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Following the trail of Rebel and Misja.

A century-later confirmation of *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) in Albania and a critical reassessment of its Balkan range.

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Abstract

The presence of *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) in Albania (Misja, 2005) is confirmed, documenting a population on the west-facing slopes of Mali i Thatë (1565–2088 m). The species appears locally abundant and occupies a larger area than previously recognised. The Balkan population, previously described as ssp. *occidentalis*, is here considered a geographical race to emphasise its disjunct distribution, a status further supported by the limited resolution of available mitochondrial COI data. The species' occurrence on Mt. Pelister (North Macedonia) is uncertain and is treated as data deficient. Implications for its distribution, conservation status, and management in the Balkans are discussed.

Key words

Pseudochazara geyeri — *Pseudochazara geyeri occidentalis* — Papilionoidea — Nymphalidae — Satyrinae — distribution — conservation — Mali i Thatë — Albania — Balkans.

Introduction

Pseudochazara geyeri, originally named and illustrated (Fig. 1a-b) as *Satyrus Geyeri* Bisch. by Herrich-Schäffer in 1846, was collected from the southern slopes of Mount Ararat located in Iğdır Province, eastern Turkey and was subsequently given a brief formal description by him in 1851 (Fig. 1c). Fruhstorfer (1911) later described the species and its subspecies *aristonius* from Amasia. *P. geyeri* is treated here according to the taxonomic classification of [Taymans and Cuvelier](#) (2025).

[Drenowsky](#) (1921) records the presence of this taxon in Europe. His research dates from 1917–1918 in the region surrounding the towns of Ohrid and Resen (historically Resna) as well as the region between the two large lakes, Ohrid and Prespa. This region includes the Galičica Mountains, the Baba Mountains (Pelister range) to the east of Resen, and the Bigla Mountains to the north of the town. Of particular interest is Drenowsky's observation at the end of page 165, in which he notes: "Die asiatischen Arten *Satyrus geyeri* und *Ino capitalis*, von welchen man die erste zahlreich in einer Höhe von 1600–2000 m antrifft, fehlen gänzlich auf dem benachbarten Babagebirge. In the introduction to this publication, Drenowsky specifies Koscharispitze (1900 m) as the locality representing his research area in the Baba Mountains (Pelister region) where he did not find a population. In 1930, Drenowsky reported that *P. geyeri* was widely distributed and frequently encountered in the high limestone rocky areas of Mt. Galičica, above 1600 metres, and, at that time, known only from the western and southern slopes.

In 1931, [Rebel & Zerny](#) described this population as a new subspecies, originally formatted as: *Satyrus (Hipparchia) Geyeri* (H. S.) *occidentalis* nov. subsp., based on specimens from Alexander Drenowski, collected on Mt. Galičica at 1600–1900 m on 24.vii.1918. He noted that they differ from the Armenian material by having a paler underside of the wings and a considerably broader whitish postmedian band on the hindwing underside. Relevant printscreens and additional details are provided below (Fig. 2 a-d).

The distribution of *Pseudochazara geyeri* has been gradually clarified through successive studies.

[Holik](#) (1949) mentions: "Mittlerweile wurde die Art auch anderwärts auf dem Balkan aufgefunden. Es lagen 8 ♂♂ von der Petrina-Planina vor, die wahrscheinlich zur gleichen Unterart gehören."

"Petrina Planina" may not be a new area as suggested, since the name is also recorded for the Mount Galičica area ([Aistleitner & Gros](#), 2020).

Higgins (1970) reported the taxon as: "In Europe known only from mountains in Albania and in SE. Yugoslavia north of Lake Ochrid." Subsequently, Higgins (1975) refined this account, stating: "*P. g. occidentalis* Rebel & Zerny 1931. Range. Albania, a few isolated colonies known near Lake Ochrid."

[Gross](#) (1978) summarises the global range of *P. geyeri* as extending from Albania and Macedonia to eastern Anatolia, reaching as far as Mount Ararat and Kars. He further described two new subspecies from Turkey: *P. g. karsicola* from Kars, representing populations from northern and eastern Anatolia, and *P. g. selim* from Erciyas Dağı near Kayseri, west of Gürün, central Anatolia. Schaidler and Jakšić (1989), provide a map of the species' distribution in North Macedonia (Map 164), indicating its occurrence from Mount Galičica to Mount Pelister.

299. 300. id. foem.

301. 302. *Satyrus Geyeri* Bisch. Von Herrn M. Wagner, von der Südseite des Ararat. Der Mann ist nicht verschieden.

Geyeri m. **Sppl.** 301, 302.

Fuscogrisea, fascia ochraceo-testacea, limbum versus arcubus acutissimis terminata, praesertim subtus.

Diese schöne Art brachte Herr M. Wagner in mehreren Exemplaren von der Südseite des Ararat mit. Die drei Exemplare, welche ich sah, waren Weiber, eines viel kleiner als das abgebildete, eines in der Grundfarbe bleicher. Sie steht in der Färbung der *Beroë*, in der Zeichnung der *Hippolyte* am nächsten. Die Farbe ist braungrau, die Binde weisslicher; letztere ist auf den Vorderflügeln wurzelwärts in Zelle 1*b* und auf Rippe 4 nicht so scharf eingebogen als bei *Hippolyte*, die Bogen an ihrer Aussenseite sind auf den Hinterflügeln viel tiefer und bilden auf den Rippen viel schärfere Zacken wurzelwärts. Die Augen in Zelle 2 u. 5 der Vorderflügel und in Zelle 2 der Hinterflügel sind immer gekernt. Unten sind die Vorderflügel beinfarben, gegen die Spitze weissgrau, die Begrenzung der Binde und die beiden Querflecke der Mittelzelle grob schwarz. Die Hinterflügel haben schneeweisse Franzen und Rippen, und solche Begrenzung der dunklen Wurzelhälfte. Diese ist von einer scharfen und groben schwarzen Linie, eingefasst und von mehreren durchzogen. Die Bogen vor dem Saume sind tief schwarz und bilden saumwärts eher Spitzen als Bogen. In Zelle 2 steht ein schwarzer Punkt. — Der später erhaltene Mann weicht gar nicht ab.

Fig. 1a. Left: first illustration of *Pseudochazara geyeri* (*Satyrus Geyeri* Bisch.) by Herrich-Schäffer, 1846 (pl. 62, fig. 301-302).

Fig. 1b. Right, top: original name *Satyrus Geyeri* Bisch. as published by Herrich-Schäffer, 1846 (page 163).

Fig. 1c. Right, bottom: short description of *Satyrus Geyeri* Bisch. (now *Pseudochazara geyeri*) by Herrich-Schäffer, 1851 (page 13).

Die Lepidopterenfauna Albanien.

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Im Jahre 1917 und 1918 war der bulgarische Entomologe Alexander K. Drenowski als Offizier im Dorfe Konsko in der Galičica Planina (Tomorosgebirge) stationiert und durchforschte von hier aus mit großem Erfolg dieses Gebirge, wie auch die Umgebungen von Ochrida und Resna und die Bigla-Planina nördlich dieser Stadt. Einige außerordentlich interessante Entdeckungen verdanken wir Drenowski, so die erste Auffindung von *Satyrus Geyeri* und *Procris capitalis* in Europa und die erste Feststellung des Vorkommens von *Melanargia russiae* auf der Balkanhalbinsel (Lit-Verz. 16, 22).

Endemismen (21).

Ein nach drei Weltrichtungen von binnenländischen Territorien begrenztes, kleines Land, wie Albanien, kann selbstredend nicht viele wirkliche Endemismen beherbergen. Daher sind die heute noch als Endemismen erscheinenden Arten und Lokalformen, die 1·4% des Faunenbestandes betragen, auch noch in den Hauptgruppen der Faunenelemente mitgezählt.

Diese scheinbaren Endemismen sind:

- Parnassius apollo dardanus* Rbl. (6).
- mnemosyne Parvisii* Tur. (7).
- Erebia gorge albanica* Rbl. (87).
- Satyrus briseis albanica* R. und Z. (76).
- Geyeri occidentalis* R. und Z. (79).
- Pararge hiera arnauta* R. und Z. (88).
- Coenonympha satyriou skypetarum* R. und Z. (97).

¹ H. Rebel, Zur Frage der europäischen Faunenelemente. Ann. d. Naturhist. Museums, Wien, 46. Bd., 1931, p. 49—55.

Fig. 2a. Global research area of Drenowsky as described in Rebel & Zerny (1931), p. 45.

Konsko: village of Konjsko on the shore of Lake Prespa. Galičica Planina: Mount Galičica. Resna: Resen. Localities lie outside the Principality of Albania (1914-1925).

Fig. 2b. Original name, first mentioned in the article: *Satyrus Geyeri occidentalis* R. und Z. (79) (Rebel & Zerny 1931, p. 49).

79. *Satyrus (Hipparchia) Geyeri* (H. S.) *occidentalis* nov. subsp. — Dren. I, p. 1651; II, p. 136, 164, 166, 171, 175, 176². Tafel, Fig. 5, ♂, 6, ♀ (Unterseite).

Die Art wurde zum ersten Male in Europa von Drenowski auf der Galičica Pl. in 1600 bis 1900 m Höhe am 24. VII. 1918 gesammelt. Es liegen uns 2 Pärchen vor, die sich von armenischen Stücken deutlich dadurch unterscheiden, daß die Unterseite aller Flügel blässer und die weißliche Postmedianbinde der Hinterflügelunterseite beträchtlich breiter ist.

Die Art ist sonst nur aus dem nordöstlichen Kleinasien, aus Armenien und Kurdistan bekannt.

Fig. 2c. Description of *P. geyeri occidentalis* (Rebel & Zerny 1931, p. 74).

Fig. 2d. Photographs in "Tafel 1" (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) of the ♂ upper- and ♀ underside of *P. geyeri occidentalis*.

[Koutroubas](#) (1993) provided the first record of *P. g. occidentalis* in Greece, based on specimens collected in 1992 on Oros Malimadi.

In Hesselbarth *et al.* (1995a-b), the cited global range is: "Verbreitung: Die Art fehlt in den Levante-Staaten, in Irak und Iran. Sie ist lokal im westlichen teil der Balkanhalbinsel, in der Türkei und im westlichen Transkaukasien verbreitet." The accompanying map in Hesselbarth *et al.* (1995c, map 289 on p. 794), indicates a single recorded locality in the western half of Turkey and numerous scattered localities throughout the eastern half. *Eumenis geyeri aristoniscus* Fruhstorfer [1911]; *Satyrus geyeri occidentalis* Rebel & Zerny 1931; *Pseudochazara geyeri selim* Gross, 1978 and *Pseudochazara geyeri karsicola* Gross, 1978 are treated as "Infrasubspezifisches" taxon.

Tolman (1997) summarised the distribution of *P. g. occidentalis* as extending across mountains near Lake Ohrid in Albania, the Galičica Plateau and Pelister Massif in south-western North Macedonia (1500–1700 m), and southwards into north-western Greece on Mt Malimadi and the Triklarion Mountains (1450–1650 m).

[Slivov & Abadjiev](#) (1999) reported this species based on samples kept in the collection of Al. Slivov (IBER) as new to the Bulgarian fauna from Slavyanka Mt. and Belasitsa Mt. But [Hristova & Beshkov](#) (2017) note that the earlier record of *P. geyeri* from Slavyanka and Belasitsa mountains ([Slivov & Abadjiev](#) 1999) was based on mislabelled specimens, and following [Koley](#) (2002), the species is excluded from the Bulgarian fauna. An important quotation in Slivov & Abadjiev (1999, p. 146) questions, for the first time, the occurrence of the species in Albania: "The reported occurrence of the species in Albania (Tolman & Lewington 1997: 201) is very possible but still not confirmed

The first record showing a clearly defined locality in Albania (Fig. 3a), on Mali i Thatë, was published by Misja (2005) based on personal observations (Fig. 3b).

Pseudochazara geyeri Herich - Schiffermüller, 1846 - Flutura e Geyerit. (tab. XXV, 3)

Tek ♂, ana e sipërme e flatrave e verdhë - gri, me zonën bazale dhe paraanësore më të errët; flatrat e përparme me 2 shirita të shkurtër në qelizën e mesme, 1 të gjatë që përshkon tërë flatrën në zonën diskale dhe 2 njolla "sy" me pikë të bardhë; flatrat e pasme pa njolla. Ana e poshtme e flatrave të përparme me ngjyrën bazë më të çelët dhe figurën më të errësuar se të anës së sipërme; tek ♀ ngjyra bazë e anës së sipërme të flatrave më e zbardhur, figura më e zbehtë se tek ♂.

Takohet në faqe kodrinash e malesh të thatë e gurishtorë, shkon deri në rreth 1000 - 2000 m. Fluturon në korrik - gusht. Jep një brezni. Nuk njihen bimët ku jeton vemja.

Përhapur në Maqedoni.

Takuar (harta 144), Prespë, Goricë

Fig. 3a. *P. geyeri* (Map 144 in Misja 2005): blackened dot indicates locality. Image can be enlarged by clicking.

Fig. 3b. Paragraph on *P. geyeri* in Misja (2005). "Occurs in Macedonia. Encountered (Map 144), Prespa, Gorica".

P. geyeri was documented from Galičica National Park by [Krpač et al.](#) (2011) and later assessed as Vulnerable in North Macedonia by [Krpač and Darcemont](#) (2012). Tshikolovets (2011) lists the range as the central Balkans, Asia Minor, Transcaucasia, and north-western Iran. For *P. geyeri occidentalis*, the distribution is given as border of Albania and F.Y.R.O. Macedonia (Galičica Planina Mountains), F.Y.R.O. Macedonia (Pelister Mountains), N.W. Greece (Malimadi and Triklarion Mountains), border of Greece and Bulgaria (Rhodope Mountains). This last record has since been demonstrated to be incorrect, with updated evidence provided earlier in this manuscript. Tshikolovets & Nekrutenko (2012) record the species' range as the central Balkans, Asia Minor, Transcaucasia, and north-western Iran. Within Transcaucasia, the distribution is reported from the western part of the Lesser Caucasus and the northern section of the Djavakheti–Armenian plateau. The subspecies are as follows: *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]), type locality: South Ararat, Turkey; *P. geyeri occidentalis* Rebel & Zerny, 1931, type locality: Galičica; *P. geyeri karsicola* Gross, 1978, type locality: Kars (Armenian Highlands); and *P. geyeri selim* Gross, 1978, type locality: Erciyas Dagı, Turkey. [Takáts & Mølgaard](#) (2016, Map 1A) show *P. geyeri occidentalis* occurring on Mt. Galičica and the Pelister Massif (south-west North Macedonia), near Lake Ohrid (Albania), as well as on Mt. Malimadi and the Triklarion Mountains (north-west Greece). Kudrna (2019) describes *P. geyeri* as occurring across the Balkan Peninsula. The map on p. 234 shows one dot in Bulgaria (see above) and another on the border of North Macedonia. Because of the MEB project's mapping system, these points are not highly precise and should therefore be treated with caution. Accordingly, both the Bulgarian record and the border locality are considered questionable and are not included in the present analysis. [Popović et al.](#) (2021) investigated the variation in butterfly species richness and assemblage composition along an elevational gradient and across different aspects on Mt. Galičica. *P. geyeri* occurred within the altitudinal classes 998–1152 m and 1616–1770 m, primarily on slopes with a westerly aspect (225–315°). [Pamperis](#) (2025) provides a recent map confirming the known range of *P. geyeri* in Greece, including Mt. Malimadi and the Triklarion Mountains. Oral communication further indicates a potential decline in local populations within the Greek areas. Genetic data for *Pseudochazara geyeri*, belonging to the "*mamura*" group, remain limited and are currently available only from mitochondrial COI barcoding. [Takáts & Mølgaard](#) (2016) reported a single sequence and similarly [Verovnik & Wiemers](#) (2016) included only a single sequence in the "*mamura*" group, which formed a monophyletic cluster with identical or very similar haplotypes. More recently, [Dapporto et al.](#) (2022a-b) analysed five sequences from specimens collected in Greece and North Macedonia, all representing a single haplotype. In the BOLD Data Portal, thirteen public sequences of *P. geyeri* are available, representing specimens from eastern Turkey, North Macedonia and Greece. All of these sequences are assigned to a single BIN: [BOLD:AAD3197](#).

Observations

On 02.viii.2025 the area north-east above Alarup (Fig. 5d, 5i-j) was surveyed by the first author.

The first rocky slopes with scattered to closed bushes, between 1250 and 1500 m, held several species such as *Colias croceus* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Lycaena phlaeas* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Lysandra bellargus* (Rottemburg, 1775), different *Polyommatus* species, *Issoria lathonia* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Brintesia circe* (Fabricius, 1775), *Chazara briseis* (Linnaeus, 1764), *Hipparchia statilinus* (Hufnagel, 1766), *Lasiommata megera* (Linnaeus, 1767) and *Maniola jurtina* (Linnaeus, 1758), which were rather common at the upper limit of this range, marking the transition to open rocky ground. The lower vegetation was notably dry, except in small shaded pockets beneath the bushes and in areas sheltered from direct sunlight.

Between 1500 and 1750 m the habitats were very dry, with some areas exhibiting pronounced aridity. The number of butterflies was markedly lower throughout this range. From 1565 m *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) was observed. Also present were *Papilio machaon* Linnaeus, 1758, *Pieris mannii* (Mayer, 1851), a few Lycaenidae species, *Hyponphele lycaon* (Kühn, 1774), *Lasiommata maera* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Satyrus ferula* (Fabricius, 1793).

Between 1750 and 2000 m *P. geyeri* (Fig. 5f) was local but present in good numbers. Newly observed, though in small numbers, were *Aricia agestis* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Polyommatus damon* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Melitaea didyma* (Esper, [1778]), *Arethusana arethusa* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Coenonympha pamphilus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Erebia melas* (Herbst, 1796) and *Melanargia russiae* (Esper, [1783]).

Above 2000 m *P. geyeri* (Fig. 5e) was recorded up to 2088 m, while *E. melas* increased in numbers.

On 09.viii.2025, the east/north-east area above Bletas (Fig. 5g-h) was also visited by the second author. The ecological characteristics of the second environment were found to be very similar to those of the first one. The areas surrounding Bletas were extremely arid and overgrazed due to the sheep and goat herds present in the area. As the altitude increases, above 1250 and 1300 metres, grazing was less intense and numerous butterfly species were observed such as *C. croceus*, *A. arethusa*, *H. statilinus*, *C. briseis*, *H. lycaon*, *Hesperia comma* (Linnaeus, 1758) and several species of *Polyommatus*. The herbaceous vegetation was mostly dry with the exception of aromatic essences, of which blooms were abundant, *Satureya montana* L. 1753 in particular. Furthermore, the first sporadic specimens of *P. geyeri* in this location were observed starting from an altitude of 1550-1570 metres in sympatry with some other butterfly species such as *Hipparchia fagi* (Scopoli, 1763), *L. maera*, *L. megera*, *S. ferula*, *Polyommatus* species and *B. circe*. *P. geyeri* specimens at this altitude were mostly worn, especially the males, indicating that they had been already in flight for several days (Fig. 5b-c).

The highest densities were found at altitudes between 1700 and 2000 meters, where multiple individuals could be observed simultaneously. At the highest altitudes, both males and females were much fresher, with some having even recently emerged (Fig. 5a). Here, the species was found in sympatry with *E. melas*, although it was noted that the latter preferred microhabitats of limestone outcrops, while *P. geyeri* preferred dry meadows with accumulations of gravel and rocks.

Fig. 4. Combined observations on Mali i Thatë (Albania) by Giuseppe Molinari and Sylvain Cuvelier. adapted from Google Earth. N= North, S= South.

Fig. 5a. *Pseudochazara geyeri* ♀ ups, Mali i Thatë, east of Bletas (Albania), 09.viii.2025 (Photo: Giuseppe Molinari)

Fig.5b. *Pseudochazara geyeri* ♂ uns, Mali i Thatë, east of Bletas (Albania), 09.viii.2025 (Photo: Giuseppe Molinari)

Fig. 5c. *Pseudochazara geyeri* ♂ uns, Mali i Thatë, east of Bletas (Albania), 09.viii.2025 (Photo: Giuseppe Molinari)

Fig. 5d. Micro habitat of *Pseudochazara geyeri*, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 2060 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 5e. *Pseudochazara geyeri* ♂ uns, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 2060 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 5f. *Pseudochazara geyeri* ♂ uns, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 1930 m asl , 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Fig. 5g. Habitat of *Pseudochazara geyeri*, Mali i Thatë, east of Bletas (Albania), 1650 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Giuseppe Molinari)
Fig. 5h. Habitat of *Pseudochazara geyeri*, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 2050 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Giuseppe Molinari)

Fig. 5i. Habitat of *Pseudochazara geyeri*, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 1930 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Sylvain Cuvelier)
Fig. 5j. Habitat of *Pseudochazara geyeri*, Mali i Thatë, east of Alarup (Albania), 2064 m asl, 02.viii.2025 (Photo: Sylvain Cuvelier)

Results and discussion

The title "Die Lepidopterenfauna Albaniens" (Rebel & Zerny 1931) likely contributed to the idea that *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) occurred in Albania, while the shifting historical borders may have been overlooked by subsequent authors.

The frontiers have changed several times since the discovery of *P. geyeri*, and the localities cited in Drenowsky (1921, 1930) and Rebel & Zerny (1931) are today outside Albania, and were not within its historical borders either (see maps). Two maps (Fig. 7–8) from the period of Drenowsky's records (1917–1918) show that Mali i Thatë was at best only marginally within Albanian territory.

The comment in Slivov & Abadjiev (1999), "The reported occurrence of the species in Albania (Tolman & Lewington 1997: 201) is very possible but still not confirmed." was the first indication that *P. geyeri* had no verified records in Albania at the time.

The first record with a clearly defined locality in Albania (Fig. 3a), on Mali i Thatë, was later published by Misja (2005) based on personal observations (Fig. 3b).

Map 6a. The Principality of Albania in 1916 with the national border. ([url](#))

Map 6b. Detail of Map 7a focusing on the transboundary region of Lake Ohrid and Lake Prespa.

Fig. 7a. Carte ethnographique de l'Albanie 1918. Blue line: frontier of Albania. (Lako & Bowman 1918)

Fig. 7b. Detail of Map 8a focusing on the transboundary region of Lake Ohrid and Lake Prespa.

The presence of *P. geyeri* has now been reconfirmed for Albania, with the species recorded on Mali i Thatë between 1565 and 2088 m. This represents the first verified record since Misja (2005) and shows the species occurring at considerably higher elevations than reported by Popović *et al.* (2021) on Mt. Galičica, where the highest altitudinal range was 1616–1770 m. On the basis of the observations by both authors, the species is likely to have a broader distribution on the western slopes of Mali i Thatë.

While compiling locality data from several sources (GBIF, iNaturalist, and Observation International) we discovered two observations (url1; url2) that were unknown to us during our August 2025 survey. These records were not included in the latest update of the *Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas 09.i.2025*, and were also absent from a recent GBIF download (27.x.2025), indicating that they were only recently added to the Observation.org platform.

The nearest population in Greece, on the Triklarion Mountains, lies roughly 30 km away as the crow flies. A small part of this mountain extends into Albania, with its highest point, Maja Vejskovarit, at 1533 m, but it is uncertain whether the elevation there is sufficient for *P. geyeri*. Between these areas, the peak of Mali i Ivanit (1768 m) may reach a suitable altitude, although earlier surveys have not recorded the species there.

Pelister National Park presents an intriguing case regarding the presence of *P. geyeri*.

Drenowsky (1921) reported having surveyed multiple areas near Ohrid, including the Baba Mountains (Pelister range). However, in his 1930 publication, he recorded *P. geyeri* only from Mt. Galičica, with no observations from the Baba Mountains.

Map 164 in Schaidler and Jakšić (1989) clearly marks two dots in the Pelister area and is the only source, known to us, to have ever provided direct information on *P. geyeri* in this region.

Predrag Jakšić (oral communication) reported that Schaidler surveyed Pelister before him and was very familiar with the terrain, marking two locations (10 × 10 km squares) for *P. geyeri* in Schaidler & Jakšić (1989). However, Jakšić himself has never observed the species in the field and Pelister Mt was one of his favorite places where he went many times. More than 35 years have passed since this monograph was published, and several subsequent sources (Tolman 1997, Tshikolovets 2011, [Takáts & Mølgaard 2016](#)) appear to have repeated the reported presence on Pelister based solely on Schaidler & Jakšić (1989) although *P. geyeri* was absent from two studies ([Micevski & Micevski 2002/2003](#); [Micevski & Micevski 2004/2005](#)) dedicated to Pelister National Park. Nikola and Branko Micevski, who have extensively surveyed the area, confirmed that they are not aware of any other publication providing evidence of *P. geyeri* in Pelister National Park.

The geological framework of the three massifs, Mount Pelister (North Macedonia), Mount Galičica and Mali i Thatë (Albania), illustrates a clear distinction in substrate, relief and geomorphic processes. Mount Pelister is largely comprised of crystalline rocks, mainly granites and metamorphic schists, with only minor limestones, and its relief is dominated by glacial and periglacial landforms rather than classic karst terrain ([Ribolini et al. 2018](#)). In contrast, Mount Galičica is characterised by a thick carbonate, mainly limestone, cover facilitating substantial karst development ([Gromig et al. 2018](#)). Further south, Mali i Thatë is almost entirely composed of limestone formations, exhibits karstic phenomena and functions as an anticline bridging the Ohrid and Prespa basins ([Eftimi et al. \(2002\)](#)). Together, these contrasting geologies underscore that the availability of limestone substrate and karstic features is minimal on Mount Pelister but very pronounced on the Galičica and Mali i Thatë massif. At the Locus Typicus, south of Mount Ararat, the substrate occupied by *P. geyeri* has not been documented in the literature, as far as is known to us. However, given the region's predominantly volcanic geology, it is likely that at least some habitats of *P. geyeri* do not include limestone or classical karstic features. This suggests that the crystalline and granitic substrate of Mount Pelister alone cannot exclude its potential as *P. geyeri* habitat. Given the uncertainty of *P. geyeri*'s presence and the differing geology of Mount Pelister, we consider that it warrants renewed investigation. This uncertainty is indicated in Fig. 8 with two question marks, treating the species as data deficient for the park.

Data (GBIF, iNaturalist, Observation.org) with a positional accuracy of less than 5 km are included in the distribution map (Fig. 8) together with records from [Holik \(1949\)](#), [Arnscheid & Arnscheid \(1980\)](#), [Schaidler & Jakšić \(1989\)](#), [Krpáč et al. \(2011\)](#), Roger Vila's database and our personal observations from Albania and Greece.

Fig. 8. Distribution map of *P. geyeri* across the western Balkans, including historical and recent records.

The recent analysis by [Paparisto & Cuvelier \(2025\)](#) of Albania's Red Lists, incorporating data from the most recent [Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas 09.i.2025](#), provided a basis for reassessing the conservation status of *P. geyeri* in the country. Historically, the national Red List status of *P. geyeri* in Albania had changed from Vulnerable (VU – A1b) in 2006, to Vulnerable (VU) in 2013, and to Near Threatened (NT) in 2022. These changes were driven by the lack of new observations since the record by [Misja \(2005\)](#), coupled with increasing pressures on the species' habitat, including degradation and climate-change impacts on the dry, stony slopes at higher altitudes.

As shown in the comparative overview presented in the BCE website for *P. geyeri* ([url](#)), which contrasts the European Red List assessments of 2010 and 2025, the species had been assessed as Least Concern (LC) in 2010. The new European Red List of [van Swaay et al. \(2025\)](#), adopting the IUCN criteria, now classifies the species as Endangered (EN) under the criteria B1ab(iii,v)+B2ab(iii,v), reflecting its restricted range (both Extent of Occurrence [EOO] and Area of Occupancy [AOO]), its occurrence in few localities, and evidence of continuing declines in habitat quality and population size.

The findings presented here, raise questions about how the species' status should be interpreted at both European and national level. Given the presence of a seemingly strong population on Mali i Thatë, combined with the possible absence of *P. geyeri* from Mt. Pelister, it is worth considering whether the European EN classification fully reflects the situation in this part of its range. Similarly, the recent observations prompt a review of the Near Threatened (NT) status in the Albanian Red List (2022), as the local abundance and extent on Mali i Thatë may indicate that the species is more secure nationally than previously assumed, while still warranting careful monitoring to ensure population stability and assess potential threats.

The taxonomic status of all the described subspecies of *P. geyeri* remains complex and should be approached cautiously. Morphological traits, including colouration and wingspan, are reported to be variable and appear to depend on local environmental conditions. Hesselbarth *et al.* (1995a-b) synonymised the described subspecies, emphasising the difficulty of defining stable taxonomic units within the species. Only mitochondrial data (COI gene) are currently available for this group, which provides limited resolution for distinguishing closely related populations. The BOLD sequence cluster [BIN:AAD3197](#), representing *P. geyeri*, currently includes records identified as multiple other *Pseudochazara* taxa: *Pseudochazara graeca* (Staudinger, 1870), *Pseudochazara mamurra* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]), *Pseudochazara beroe* (Freyer, [1844]), *Pseudochazara amydone* Brown, 1976, *Pseudochazara schahkuhensis* (Staudinger, 1881), *Pseudochazara sintenisi* (Staudinger, 1895), *Pseudochazara daghestana* (Holik, 1955), *Pseudochazara kermana* Eckweiler, 2004, *Pseudochazara alpina* (Staudinger, 1878) and *Pseudochazara lydia* (Staudinger, 1878). This suggests that the BIN contains specimens from several species, indicating either incomplete lineage sorting, misidentifications, or the limited discriminatory power of COI barcoding within this complex. Taken together, both morphological variability and the limited molecular evidence, it is most appropriate to treat the Balkan population as a geographical race, *P. geyeri occidentalis*, reflecting the clearly disjunct nature of the Balkan population relative to the species' main distribution in Asia

Conclusions

This study confirms the single previously reported record of *Pseudochazara geyeri* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1846]) in Albania by [Misja](#) (2005), documenting a clearly defined population on the west-facing slopes of Mali i Thatë between 1565 and 2088 m. The species appears locally well established and may occupy a broader area of suitable high-altitude habitat than previously recognised. The presence of the species on Mt. Pelister in North Macedonia needs verification. While *P. geyeri* is listed as Endangered (EN) on the European Red List 2025 and Near Threatened (NT) on the Albanian Red List 2022, these observations suggest that the Albanian population may be more secure than assumed, although it remains vulnerable. The Balkan population is tentatively regarded as a geographical race (*P. geyeri occidentalis*), pending further morphological and genome-wide genomic research, given its disjunct distribution and the limited resolution of mitochondrial COI data. Conservation efforts should focus on maintaining habitat integrity on Mali i Thatë and exploring adjacent massif zones to clarify the species' regional distribution.

Author contribution

Sylvain Couvelier: conceptualization, field work, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing. Giuseppe Molinari: conceptualization, field work, analysis, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing.

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References

- Aistleitner E. & Gros P. 2020. Zur Chorologie und Phaenologie der Dickkopf-Falter Europas, mit Schwerpunkten in den Ost- und Südalpen, in Italien sowie auf der Iberischen Halbinsel (Lepidoptera, Hesperidae). — *Linzer biologische Beiträge* 52(1): 5-29. ([url](#))
- Arnscheid W. & Arnscheid W. 1980. Reiseeindrücke aus jugoslawisch Mazedonien. — *Mitteilungen der Westfälischen Entomologen*, Bochum 4(4): 39–52.
- Butterfly Conservation Europe. 2025. Grey Asian Grayling (*Pseudochazara geyeri*). ([url](#)) (Accessed 2.xi.2025).
- Couvelier S. & Papparisto A. 2025. Fluturat e Shqipërisë Atlas 09.i.2025. — *Chronicles Fluturat e Shqipërisë* 2025(1): 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14947890>
- Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Couvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022a. The Atlas of mitochondrial diversity of Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 00, 1–7. ([url](#))
- Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Couvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022b. The Atlas of mitochondrial diversity of Western Palearctic butterflies. Appendix S1. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 00, 1–7. ([url](#))

- Drenowsky A. 1921. Zur Lepidopterenfauna Makedoniens. — *Zeitschrift für wissenschaftliche Insektenbiologie* 16: 164-166. ([url](#))
- Drenowsky A. 1930. Beitrag zur Lepidopterenfauna S.W. Macedoniens. — *Zeitschrift Bulg. Akad. Wissensch.* 42: 120-177.
- Eftimi R., Skende P. & Zoto J. 2002. Isotope study of the connection of Ohrid and Prespa lakes. — *Geologica Balcanica* 32(1): 43-49. ([url](#))
- Fruhstorfer H. 1911. *Satyrus geyeri aristochinus*. — In: Seitz, A. (ed.), *Die Gross-Schmetterlinge der Erde*, Band 9. Stuttgart. 1197 p. ([url](#))
- Gromig R., Mechernich S., Ribolini A., Wagner B., Zanchetta G., Isola I., Bini M. & Dunai T. 2018. Evidence for a Younger Dryas deglaciation in the Galicica Mountains (FYROM) from cosmogenic ³⁶Cl. — *Quaternary international* 464: 352–363. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2017.07.013>
- Gross F. 1978. Beitrag zur Systematik von *Pseudochazara* Arten (Lep. Satyridae). — *Atalanta* 9: 41–103. ([url](#))
- Herrich-Schäffer G. A. W. [1846]. *Systematische Bearbeitung der Schmetterlinge von Europa, zugleich als Text, Revision und Supplement zu Jakob Hubner's Sammlung europäischer Schmetterlinge*. Erster Band. Die Tagfalter: 1-164, pl. 1-134 (Papilionides), pl. 1-7 (Hesperides). — Regensburg: G. J. Manz (Ed.). [163](#), [pl. 62](#), [fig. 301-302](#)
- Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]. *Systematische Bearbeitung der Schmetterlinge von Europa, zugleich als Text, Revision und Supplement zu Jakob Hubner's Sammlung europäischer Schmetterlinge*. Sechster und letzter Band. Nachtrag zum ersten Bande: 1-31. ([13](#))
- Hesselbarth G., van Oorschot H. & Wagener S. 1995a, *Die Tagfalter der Türkei unter Berücksichtigung der angrenzenden Länder*. Volume 1-2. — Selbstverlag Sigbert Wagener, Bocholt. 1354 p.
- Hesselbarth G., van Oorschot H. & Wagener S. 1995b, *Die Tagfalter der Türkei unter Berücksichtigung der angrenzenden Länder*. Volume 3. — Selbstverlag Sigbert Wagener, Bocholt. 847 p.
- Higgins L. 1975. *The Classification of European Butterflies*. — William Collins Sons & Co. Ltd., Glasgow. 320 p. Higgins L. & Riley N. 1970. *A field Guide to the Butterflies of Britain and Europe*. — London: Collins (Ed.). 380 p.
- Holik O. 1949. Ueber die Gattung Satyrus L. (Lepidoptera, Satyridae) — *Zeitschrift der Wiener Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 34 : 98-105. ([url](#))
- Hristova H. & Beshkov S. 2017. Checklist of the Superfamilies Hesperioidea and Papilionoidea (Insecta: Lepidoptera) of Bulgaria, with Application of the IUCN Red List Criteria at National Level. — *Acta zoologica bulgarica* 69 (1): 105-114. ([url](#))
- Kolev Z. 2002. Critical notes on some recent butterfly records (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea & Hesperioidea) from Bulgaria and their source collection. — *Phegea*, 30 (3): 95-101. ([url](#))
- Koutroubas A. 1993. *Pseudochazara geyeri occidentalis* (Rebel & Zerny, 1931) espèce nouvelle pour la Grèce (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae: Satyrinae). — *Phegea* 21(2): 45-46. ([url](#))
- Krpač V., Darcemont C., Krpač M. & Lemonnier-Darcemont M. 2011. Fauna of butterflies (Papilionoidea) in the National Park Galičica, Republic of Macedonia. — *Nota lepidopterologica* 34(1): 49–78. ([url](#))
- Krpač V. & Darcemont C. 2012. Red list of butterflies (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea & Papilionoidea) for Republic of Macedonia. — *Revue Ecologie (Terre Vie)* 67: 117–122. ([url](#))
- Kudrna 2019. Distribution of Butterflies and Skippers in Europe (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera, Grypocera). 24 Years Mapping European Butterflies (1995-2019) Final report. — Prachatice: Společnost pro Ochranu Motýlů (SOM). 364 p.
- Lako N. & Bowman I. 1918. *Carte ethnographique de l'Albanie* [Map]. — [Paris?: s.n.] [Map] Retrieved from the Library of Congress. ([url](#)) (Accessed 27.x.2025).
- Micevski N. & Micevski B. (2002/2003). Butterfly fauna (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea & Hesperioidea) in the National Park Pelister. — *Annual. Biol. Skopje*. 55–56: 75–98. ([url](#))
- Micevski B. & Micevski N. (2004/2005). A biogeographical and ecological analysis of the butterfly fauna of Pelister National Park. — *Biologia Macedonica* 57/58: 89–98. ([url](#))

- Misja K. 2005. *Fluturat e Shqipërisë. Macrolepidoptera (Rhopalocera, Bombyces & Sphinges, Noctuidae, Geometridae)*. — Akademia e Shkencave e Shqipërisë, Instituti i Kërkimeve Biologjike, Tiranë, 247 p. [in Albanian]. ([url](#))
- Pamperis L. 2025. *The Butterflies of Greece — New maps distribution of species 3.3'' and new chart 4.5''*. ([url](#))
- Paparisto A. & Cuvelier S. 2025. Unlocking the secrets of Albania's endangered butterfly populations: a comprehensive review of Red Lists and strategic approaches for enhancing conservation efforts to better target species and priority areas. — *Chronicles Fluturat e Shqipërisë* 2025(1): 20-24. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14885213
- Popović M., Micevski B. & Verovnik R. 2021. Effects of elevation gradient and aspect on butterfly diversity on Galičica Mountain in the Republic of Macedonia (south-eastern Europe). — *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation* 44.1: 67-79. ([url](#))
- Rebel H. & Zerny H. 1931. Die Lepidopterenfauna Albaniens. — *Denkschriften der Akademie der Wissenschaften Wien, mathematischnaturwissenschaftliche Klasse* 103: 37–161. ([url](#))
- Ribolini A., Bini M., Isola I., Spagnolo M., Zanchetta G., Pellitero-Ondicol R., Mechernich S., Gromig R., Dunai T., Wagner B. & Milevski I. 2018. An Oldest Dryas glacier expansion on Mount Pelister (Former Yugoslavian Republic of Macedonia) according to 10Be cosmogenic dating. — *Journal of the Geological Society* 175(1): 100-110. <https://doi.org/10.1144/jgs2017-038>
- Schaider P. & Jakšić P. 1989. *Die Tagfalter von Jugoslawisch Mazedonien Diurna (Rhopalocera und Hesperiiidae)* — Selbstverlag Paul Scheider, München, 199 p.
- Slivov A. & Abadjiev S. 1999. Two Pseudochazara species, new for Bulgaria (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae: Satyrinae). — *Phegea* 27(4): 145-146. ([url](#))
- Takáts K. & Mølgaard M. 2016. Partial mtCOI-sequences of Balkanic species of *Pseudochazara* (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) reveal three well-differentiated lineages. — *Entomologica romanica* 19: 21–40. ([url](#))
- Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. 2025. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224
- Tolman T. & Lewington R. 1997. *Field Guide of the Butterflies of Britain and Europe*. — Harper Collins Publishers, London, 320 p.
- Tshikolovets V. 2011. *Butterflies of Europe & the Mediterranean area*. — Pardubice: Tshikolovets (Ed.). 544 p.
- Tshikolovets V. & Nekrutenko (†) Y. 2012. *The Butterflies of Caucasus and Transcaucasia (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and Russian Federation)*. — Kyiv / Pardubice: Tshikolovets Publications, 423 p.
- Van Swaay C., Warren M., Ellis S., Clay J., Bellotto V., Allen D. & Trottet A. 2025. *Measuring the pulse of European biodiversity. European Red List of Butterflies*. — Brussels, Belgium: European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2779/935927>
- Verovnik R. & Wiemers M. 2016. Species delimitation in the Grayling genus *Pseudochazara* (Lepidoptera, Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) supported by DNA barcodes. — *Zookeys* 600: 131–154. ([url](#))
- Wikipedia contributors, *Principality of Albania*, Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. ([url](#)) (accessed 27.x.2025).

An updated checklist of the Serbian butterflies (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea Latreille, [1802]).

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Abstract

A new checklist of the butterflies of Serbia is presented, including both scientific and vernacular names. The differences between this and previous checklists are discussed, as well as current taxonomic issues. A new Red List is proposed, with supporting justification, and species considered regionally extinct (RE) are identified.

Key words

Butterflies — Checklist — Red List — Serbia.

Introduction

The Republic of Serbia, as a European country, is situated predominantly on the Balkan Peninsula, with a smaller portion extending into the Pannonian Plain. The total area of its territory covers 88,499 km² (Fig. 1).

The first comprehensive checklist of the butterflies of Serbia, then including Macedonia, was published by [Gradojević](#) (1930–31). That list contained 168 species, with a note that many of them had been recorded only in Macedonia. After a gap of 65 years, [Zečević](#) (1996) published a list referring solely to the territory of present-day Serbia, comprising 189 species. [Jakšić & Đurić](#) (2007) produced a new checklist enumerating 193 species. For the first time, vernacular names were presented systematically, following the principle of priority, while new vernacular names were proposed for species previously lacking them. Subsequent faunistic research revealed six additional species, incorporated into the revised list by [Jakšić et al.](#) (2013). [Popović & Verovnik](#) (2018) later published an updated checklist of the butterflies of Serbia, listing 199 species. Since then, several additional species have been confirmed for the Serbian fauna. Recently, a new *European Red List of Butterflies* ([van Swaay et al.](#) 2025) has been published, introducing revised categories of species threat levels. Considering that the *Red Data Book of Serbian Butterflies* ([Jakšić](#) 2003) appeared more than two decades ago, this moment offers an appropriate opportunity to present the current faunistic status of butterfly species in Serbia, along with their vernacular names and updated conservation categories.

Taxonomic and nomenclatural framework

The systematic order of families and lower taxa, as well as species nomenclature, follows [van Nieukerken et al.](#) (2011), [Dapporto et al.](#) (2022), [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025a) and [Taymans & Cuvelier](#) (2025b).

The sequence and nomenclature adopted in the first publication was also followed by [van Swaay et al.](#) (2025).

The conservation status of species is likewise presented according to [van Swaay et al.](#) (2025):

RE - Regionally Extinct

EN - Endangered

VU - Vulnerable

NT - Near Threatened

LC - Least Concern

NA - Not Applicable.

Serbian vernacular names are based on [Jakšić & Đurić](#) (2007), [Jakšić et al.](#) (2013), and later publications concerning newly recorded species.

The results are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Republic of Serbia, Relief Map ([url](#)).

Table 1. Systematic list of Serbian butterflies with vernacular names and conservation status.

SCIENTIFIC NAMES	VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
ORDER Lepidoptera Linnaeus, 1758				
SUBORDER Glossata Fabricius, 1775				
SUPERFAMILY Papilionoidea Latreille, [1802]	Дневни лептири			
FAMILY Papilionidae Latreille, [1802]	Једрилци			
SUBFAMILY Papilioninae Latreille, [1802]				
<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ветрило (Једрилац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Papilio alexanor</i> Esper, [1800]	Соколов репак	NT	NT	NT
<i>Papilio machaon</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Ластин реп	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Parnassiinae Duponchel, [1835]				
<i>Driopa mnemosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мнемозине	LC	LC	LC
<i>Parnassius apollo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Аполо	LC	LC	LC
<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Ускршњи лептир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Allanacstria cerisyi</i> (Godart, 1823)	Мирин лептир	LC	LC	LC

SCIENTIFIC NAMES	VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
FAMILY Hesperidae Latreille, 1809	Скелари			
SUBFAMILY Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925				
<i>Heteropterus morpheus</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Карирани скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Carterocephalus palaemon</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Хеленина хесперида	NT	NT	VU
SUBFAMILY Hesperinae Latreille, 1809				
<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i> (Esper, 1777)	Риђи скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hesperia comma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ливадски скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Thymelicus acteon</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Травар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i> (Poda, 1761)	Сребрни скелар	VU	VU	VU
<i>Thymelicus lineola</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	Смеђи скелар	VU	VU	VU
SUBFAMILY Pyrginae Burmeister, 1878				
<i>Spialia orbifer</i> (Hübner, [1823])	Дињицина хесперида	NT	NT	NT
<i>Spialia phlomidis</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845])	Сребрна хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Favria cribellum</i> (Eversmann, 1841)	Мозаична хесперида	VU	VU	VU
<i>Muschampia floccifera</i> (Zeller, 1847)	Тотрљанов скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Muschampia orientalis</i> Reverdin, 1913	Оријентални скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Muschampia lavatherae</i> (Esper, [1783])	Чистац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Carcharodus alceae</i> (Esper, [1780])	Слезов скелар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erynnis tages</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Тамни скелар	LC	LC	NT
<i>Pyrgus malvae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Слезова хесперида	NT	NT	NT
<i>Pyrgus carthami</i> (Hübner, [1813])	Рибар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus sidae</i> (Esper, [1784])	Липицина хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus andromedae</i> (Wallengren, 1853)	Алпијска хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus serratulae</i> (Rambur, [1839])	Загасити зујавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus armoricanus</i> (Oberthür, 1910)	Зујавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus alveus</i> (Hübner, [1803])	Проседа хесперида	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyrgus cinarae</i> (Rambur, [1839])	Пиргавац пешчаник	LC	LC	LC
FAMILY Pieridae Duponchel, [1835]	Белци			
SUBFAMILY Dismorphiinae Schatz, 1886				
<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	Балкански белац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Leptidea morsei</i> (Fenton, 1882)	Фрушкогорски белац	RE	VU	Vu
<i>Leptidea juvernica</i> Williams, 1946	Загасити белац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Горушичин белац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Coliadinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жутац (Лимуновац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias hyale</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Златни поштар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias alfacariensis</i> Ribbe, 1905	Златна осмица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias erate</i> (Esper, [1805])	Степски поштар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias croceus</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	Шафрановац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Colias myrmidone</i> (Esper, [1781])	Зановетак	RE	VU	EN
<i>Colias caucasica</i> Staudinger, 1871	Кавкаски поштар	VU	VU	VU

SCIENTIFIC NAMES		VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
SUBFAMILY Pierinae Duponchel, [1835]					
	<i>Aporia crataegi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Глоговњак (Глоговац)	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pontia edusa</i> (Fabricius, 1777)	Зелени купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris rapae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мали купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris mannii</i> (Mayer, 1851)	Далматински купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris ergane</i> (Geyer, [1828])	Планински купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жиличасти купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Pieris balcana</i> Lorković, [1969]	Балкански купусар	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Euchloe ausonia</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Чипкасти белац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Зорица	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis gruneri</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]	Мала зорица	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Anthocharis damone</i> Boisduval, 1836	Пештерска зорица	EN	EN	EN
FAMILY Riodinidae Grote, 1895		Пегавци			
SUBFAMILY Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868					
	<i>Hamearis lucina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Смеђи пегавац	LC	LC	LC
FAMILY Lycaenidae [Leach], 1815		Плавци			
SUBFAMILY Lycaeninae [Leach], 1815					
	<i>Lycaena helle</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Љубичасти дукат	NT	NT	NT
	<i>Lycaena thersamon</i> (Esper, [1784])	Пегави дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena dispar</i> ([Haworth], 1802)	Велики дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena hippothoe</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Долински дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena candens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])	Балкански дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena virgaureae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena tityrus</i> (Poda, 1761)	Бакренац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena alciphron</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Кисељаков дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lycaena phlaeas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Ватрени дукат	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Theclinae Swainson, 1831					
	<i>Thecla betulae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Брезов дукат	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Favonius quercus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Храстов репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Callophrys rubi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Купинов репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium pruni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Трњинар	VU	VU	VU
	<i>Satyrium ilicis</i> (Esper, [1779])	Храстовчић	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium w-album</i> (Knoch, 1782)	Шумски репка	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Satyrium spini</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Трњинин репка	VU	VU	VU
	<i>Satyrium acaciae</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Мали репка	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Polyommatae Swainson, 1827					
	<i>Leptotes pirithous</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Краткорепи селац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Lampides boeticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Дугорепи селац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Cacyreus marshalli</i> Butler, 1898	Мушкатлин плавац	NA	NA	NA
	<i>Celastrina argiolus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Крковин плавац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Tarucus balkanica</i> (Freyer, [1843])	Драчац	LC	LC	LC
	<i>Phengaris alcon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мали пегавац	NT	NT	NT

SCIENTIFIC NAMES	VERNACULAR NAMES	IUCN Red List Category (Serbia)	IUCN Red List Category (Europe)	IUCN Red List Category (EU27)
<i>Phengaris arion</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики пегавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Phengaris teleius</i> (Bergsträsser, 1779)	Мочварни пегавац	VU	VU	VU
<i>Pseudophilotes vicrama</i> (Moore, 1865)	Душицин плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Scolitantides orion</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Жедњаков плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Iolana iolas</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1816)	Пуцавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i> (Poda, 1761)	Зеленотрби плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido argiades</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Краткорепи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido decolorata</i> (Staudinger, 1886)	Бледи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido alcatas</i> (Hoffma[n]nsegg, 1804)	Ливадски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cupido osiris</i> (Meigen, [1829])	Озирисов плавац	LC	LC	NT
<i>Cupido minimus</i> (Fuessly, 1775)	Малени плавац	NT	NT	NT
<i>Plebejus argus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Стооки плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Plebejus idas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Идин плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i> (Bergsträsser, 1779)	Блистави плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia artaxerxes</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Тамносмеђи плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia agestis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Чапљинац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aricia anteros</i> (Freyer, 1839)	Алпијски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Kretania sephirus</i> (Frivaldszky, 1835)	Зефиоров плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Eumedonia eumedon</i> (Esper, [1780])	Здравчев плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Византијски плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Agriades optilete</i> (Knoch, 1781)	Боровничар	VU	VU	VU
<i>Lysandra bellargus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Потковичар	NT	NT	NT
<i>Lysandra coridon</i> (Poda, 1761)	Сребрнкасти плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus icarus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Гладишев плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus eros</i> (Ochsenheimer, 1808)	Планински плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus thersites</i> (Cantener, 1835)	Вучарица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Крзави плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus amandus</i> (Schneider, 1792)	Граоричар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Тиркизни плавац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus damon</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Дамон	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus admetus</i> (Esper, [1783])	Смеђан	LC	LC	LC
<i>Polyommatus ripartii</i> (Freyer, 1830)	Планински смеђан	NT	NT	NT
FAMILY Nymphalidae Swainson, 1827	Шаренци			
SUBFAMILY Limenitidinae Behr, 1864				
<i>Neptis sappho</i> (Pallas, 1771)	Грахоровац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Neptis rivularis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Медуниковац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Limenitis reducta</i> Staudinger, 1901	Козолистовац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Limenitis populi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики тополњак	LC	LC	NT
<i>Limenitis camilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Мали трепетљикар	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Heliconiinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мала седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brenthis hecate</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Белоглавичар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brenthis ino</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Инова седефица	LC	LC	LC

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<i>Brenthis daphne</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Карирана седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Госпођак	LC	LC	LC
<i>Argynnis pandora</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Пандорина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Speyeria aglaja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велика седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Fabriciana niobe</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Ниобина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Fabriciana adippe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Љубичина седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria eunomia</i> (Esper, [1800])	Старопланинска седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria graeca</i> (Staudinger, 1870)	Грчка седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria pales</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Планинска седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria selene</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Бисерна седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria euphrosyne</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Пролећна седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria dia</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Ткачева седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Boloria titania</i> (Esper, [1793])	Титанија	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Apaturinae Boisduval, 1840				
<i>Apatura iris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Таласњак	LC	LC	LC
<i>Apatura metis</i> Freyer, 1829	Панонски преливац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Apatura ilia</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мали преливац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Nymphalinae Swainson, 1827				
<i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шумска риђа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Стричковац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Vanessa atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Адмирал (Лепотић)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aglais io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Паунац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Копривар	NT	NT	NT
<i>Polygonia egea</i> (Cramer, [1775])	Војишничар	RE	LC	LC
<i>Polygonia c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Риђа седефица	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis vau-album</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Мрки многобојац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики копривар (Многобојац)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis xanthomelas</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Жутоноги многобојац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мртвачки плашт	LC	LC	NT
<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Мочварни шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Euphydryas maturna</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Жути шаренац	VU	VU	VU
<i>Melitaea trivialis</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Дивизмин шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea didyma</i> (Esper, [1778])	Црвени шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea arduinna</i> (Esper, [1783])	Фрејеров шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea phoebe</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Различков шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea ornata</i> Christoph, 1893	Кристофов шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea cinxia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Обични шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea diamina</i> (Lang, 1789)	Мрки шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea athalia</i> (Rottemburg, 1775)	Боквичин шаренац	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melitaea aurelia</i> Nickerl, 1850	Златни шаренац	LC	LC	LC
SUBFAMILY Satyrinae Boisduval, [1833]				
<i>Kirinia roxelana</i> (Cramer, 1777)	Шумски решеткар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Kirinia climene</i> (Esper, [1783])	Тимочки решеткар	LC	LC	LC

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<i>Lopinga achine</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Драганин окаш	EN	NT	NT
<i>Pararge aegeria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шумски пегавец	LC	LC	LC
<i>Lasiommata maera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велики окаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Lasiommata petropolitana</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	Планински окаш	LC	LC	NT
<i>Lasiommata megera</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	Зидни окаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Мали сатир (Мала ценонимфа)	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha rhodopensis</i> (Elwes, 1900)	Родопска ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha glycerion</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)	Кестењаста ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha leander</i> (Esper, [1784])	Ливадска ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Coenonympha orientalis</i> Rebel, [1909]	Илирска ценонимфа	NT	NT	NT
<i>Coenonympha arcania</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	Бисерна ценонимфа	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia ottomana</i> Herrich-Schäffer, [1847]	Турска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia cassioides</i> (Hochenwarth, 1792)	Планинска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia oeme</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Маслиничар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia gorge</i> (Hübner, [1804])	Загасита еребија	LC	LC	NT
<i>Erebia pandrose</i> (Borkhausen, 1788)	Снежна еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia euryale</i> (Esper, [1805])	Мала еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia ligea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Велика еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia rhodopensis</i> Nicholl, 1900	Родопска еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Erebia alberganus</i> (Prunner, 1798)	Старопланинска еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia medusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Пролећна еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia aethiops</i> (Esper, 1777)	Окаста еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia orientalis</i> Elwes, 1900	Самотна еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Erebia epiphron</i> (Knoch, 1783)	Обична еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia pronoe</i> (Esper, [1780])	Црноруба еребија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Erebia melas</i> (Herbst, 1796)	Црна еребија	NT	NT	NT
<i>Hyponephele lycaon</i> (Kühn, 1774)	Ливадски смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hyponephele lupinus</i> (Costa, 1836)	Вуков смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Aphantopus hyperantus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Окасти смеђаш	LC	LC	LC
<i>Pyronia tithonus</i> (Linnaeus, 1771)	Вратар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Maniola jurtina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Воловско око	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia larissa</i> (Geyer, [1828])	Балканска шах-табла	LC	LC	LC
<i>Melanargia galathea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Шах-табла	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia syriaca</i> (Staudinger, 1871)	Источна хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia fagi</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Шумска хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia semele</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia volgensis</i> (Mazochin-Porshnyakov, 1952)	Балканска хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i> (Hufnagel, 1766)	Јесења хипархија	LC	LC	LC
<i>Minois dryas</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Модрооки сатир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Brintesia circe</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Шумски вратар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Arethusana arethusa</i> ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)	Јесењи ливадар	LC	LC	LC
<i>Satyrus ferula</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	Велики сатир	LC	LC	LC
<i>Chazara briseis</i> (Linnaeus, 1764)	Самотњак	LC	LC	LC

Discussion and conclusions

The occurrence of the taxon *Kretania pylaon* (Fischer, 1832) in Serbia remains a matter of debate. Kudrna *et al.* (2015) provided aggregated distribution data for the *K. pylaon* complex, whereas Popović & Verovnik (2018) listed only the species *Kretania sephirus* (Frivaldszky, 1835). The first concrete evidence that these are distinct species, *Kretania pylaon brethertoni* Brown 1976, and *K. sephirus*, was provided by Coutsis & De Prins (2006), who demonstrated a difference in haploid chromosome number (*K. pylaon brethertoni* Greece $n = 37$; *K. sephirus* Bulgaria $n = 19$). The current consensus recognises them as two separate species (Dapporto *et al.* 2022; Taymans & Cuvelier 2025a; van Swaay *et al.* 2025). Taxonomically, the *Kretania pylaon* species-group complex (= *K. pylaon* complex) comprises five European species: *K. pylaon*, *K. sephirus*, *Kretania trappi* (Verity, 1927), *Kretania hespericus* (Rambur, [1839]), and *Kretania brethertoni* (Brown, 1976), whose species status is subject to debate. Balint & Fiedler (1992) recorded *K. sephirus* from Flamunda (Deliblato, Banat Province, Serbia), describing its habitat as calcareous, sandy, or loess-dominated steppe. The larvae of both species feed on plants of the genus *Astragalus*, of which 17 species occur in Serbia (Diklić 1972). Approximately 30 published studies (Jakšić 2022) deal with *K. sephirus* in Serbia; however, none provide substantiated evidence for the presence of *K. pylaon* in the country. Further cytotaxonomic research and DNA barcoding of specimens from Serbian territory could help clarify this unresolved issue.

According to Dincă *et al.* (2021), Case 14 of shared barcodes, further taxonomical research may be needed.

Lorković (1953; 1954) described *Erebia cassioides illyromacedonica* on the Macedonian side of Mt. Šar Planina as a distinct subspecies, compared to *Erebia cassioides illyrica* from Mt. Durmitor in Montenegro. We have found this subspecies at several sites (Mt. Šar Planina: Ljuboten, Piribreg, Vrbeštički jalovarnik) on the Serbian side of Mt. Šar Planina (Fig. 2).

Lopinga achine (Scopoli, 1763) was, until now, known only from a literature record in the vicinity of Majdanpek ("Univerzitetska domena" - Majdanpek District, Eastern Serbia) and, the entire collection, including this specimen, was destroyed during the Second World War (Živojinović, 1950). Remarkably, in June of this year, Mihajlo Vujić and Ivan Tot discovered a population of this species in western Srem, Vojvodina ([url](#)).

Fig. 2. *Erebia cassioides illyromacedonica*. Above: ♂ underside. Serbia, Mt. Šar Planina, Ljuboten, 2300–2490 m, 24.viii.1994. Leg. P. Jakšić. Below: ♀ underside. Serbia, Mt. Šar Planina, Piribreg, Vrbeštički Jalovarnik, 1700 m, 3–4.viii.1987, Leg. P. Jakšić.

Fig. 3. *Erebia manto* ♂ genitalia. Montenegro, Čakor, 1800 m, 18.viii.1988., Gen. slide no. 1393, Leg. P. Jakšić.

Fig. 4. *Polygonia egea* ♂ underside. Serbia, Priština, Mt. Grmija, 700 m, 1.viii.1971. Leg. P. Jakšić.

What can be expected in the future?

In their monograph devoted to the Macedonian side of Mt. Šar Planina, Krpač *et al.* (2021) list two species occurring near the border with Serbia: *Muschampia alta* (Schwingenschuss, 1942) from Vratnica and *Agriades pyrenaica dardanus* (Freyer, [1843]) without precise locality data. The authors themselves did not record these species but referred to earlier publications. Unfortunately, no field research has been conducted on the Serbian side of the Mt. Šar Planina to confirm their presence.

A similar situation applies to the species *Erebia manto* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (Fig. 3). It was confirmed in Montenegro at the site Čakor, 1800 m (Jakšić & Pešić 1995). The borderline between Montenegro and Kosovo and Metohija in that sector follows the line Starac (2426 m) - Čakor (1849 m) - Planinica (1963 m). Future fieldwork will almost certainly show that this species also occurs on the Serbian side of Mt. Čakor.

An important issue concerns species known from earlier records but not observed in the past fifty years. Two species belong to this group:

Leptidea morsei (Fenton, 1882), was only known from Mt. Fruška Gora. Specimens are preserved in the collections of Lorković (1930-1931) and the industrialist-collector Miloš Rogulja from Novi Sad (Jakšić 1993). Both records originate from Mt. Fruška Gora. The species has not been found there for the past ninety years.

Colias myrmidone (Esper, [1781]), was last recorded from Eastern Serbia: Sokolovica, Bor, and Mt. Stol, dating to 1970 (Zečević & Radovanović 1974). The species has not been observed in Serbia in the past fifty years.

These two species may therefore be regarded as regionally extinct (RE).

Another group includes species occasionally recorded beyond the limits of their natural range:

Papilio alexanor Esper, [1800], was recently recorded in western Serbia at Mt. Zlatibor, Čajetina, village Stublo (Vukajlović *et al.* 2025). The nearest known locality is Gacko in eastern Bosnia and Herzegovina (Lelo 2008), approximately 100 km in a straight line from Čajetina.

Cacyreus marshalli Butler, 1898, was discovered in the city of Niš, represented by a single specimen (Milojković *et al.* 2021).

Polygonia aegae (Cramer, [1775]), was collected by Jakšić on 1.viii.1971 at Mt. Grmija, near Priština (Fig. 4). During three decades of research on Mt. Grmija (1969–1999), this was the only specimen found. The larval host plant, *Parietaria officinalis*, is absent from that locality (Krivošej 2013). The species was later observed near Niš, in the Jelašnička Klisura Gorge (Đurić, Popović & Verovnik 2010). These three species appear to exhibit range fluctuations in response to ongoing climatic changes. As early as 1994, Ocokolić convincingly demonstrated the cyclical alternation of wet and dry periods in Serbia, and the observed range shifts correspond to these climatic oscillations.

Based on the results presented (Table 1), a total of 201 butterfly species have been recorded in the territory of Serbia. Compared with the previous checklist (Popović & Verovnik 2018), the fauna of Serbia has been enriched by three newly recorded species: *P. alexanor*: W Serbia, Stublo village, Čajetina (Vukajlović *et al.* 2025), *Tarucus balkanica* (Freyer, [1843]): SE Serbia, Pčinja Valley, Čivčije locality (Tot *et al.* 2022) and *C. marshalli*: Serbia, Niš, Palilula City Park (Milojković *et al.* 2021).

In conclusion, faunal richness is a dynamic category: over the past century, some species previously present in Serbia have disappeared, while others, until recently unknown, have been newly recorded in its territory. The conservation status of species is presented according to the categories applied in Europe, excluding the 27 EU member states (van Swaay *et al.*, 2025). The categories proposed in that publication were adopted, except for *L. morsei* and *C. myrmidone*, which are here classified as regionally extinct species (RE).

Author contribution

Predrag Jakšić: conceptualization, field work, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

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References

- Balint Z. & Fiedler K. 1992. *Plebeius sephirus* (FRIVALDSZKY, 1835) in Pannonia, with special reference to its status and ecology in Hungary. — *Oedippus* 4: 1-24. ([url](#))
- Brown J. 1976. On two previously undescribed subspecies of Lycaenidae (Lepidoptera) from Greece. — *Entomologische Berichten* 36(3): 46-47. ([url](#))
- Coutsis J. & De Prins J. 2006. The chromosome number and karyotype of *Plebeius (Plebejides) pylaon brethertoni* from Mt. Helmós, Pelopónnisos, Greece, its tentative elevation to species level, and notes about presently existing unsettled taxonomic questions in the *pylaon* species-group complex (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae). — *Phegea* 34(2): 57-60. ([url](#))
- Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodá R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila R. 2022. The atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palaearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 31, 2184-2190. doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579. S1: ([url](#))
- Diklić N. 1972. Fabales – Fabaceae – Astragalus. In: Josifović, M. (Ed) *Flore de la Republique Socialiste de Serbie*, IV: 254-405. Academie Serbe des Sciences et des Arts, Beograd. [In Serbian]
- Dincă V., Dapporto L., Somervuo P., Vodá R., Cuvelier S., Gascoigne-Pees M., Huemer P., Mutanen M., Hebert P. & Vila R. 2021. High resolution DNA barcode library for European butterflies reveals continental patterns of mitochondrial genetic diversity. — *Communications biology* 4, 1-11. ([url](#))
- Đurić M., Popović M. & Verovnik R., 2010. Jelašnica gorge – a 'hot spot' of butterfly diversity in Serbia. — *Phegea* 38(3): 111-120. ([url](#))
- Gradojević M. 1930-31. Prilog lepidoptertskoj fauni Jugoslavije. Leptirovi Srbije – Diurna. — *Glasnik jugoslovenskog entomološkog društva*, V-VI(1-2): 133-158. ([url](#))
- HabiProt 2025. *New achievements in 2025*. ([url](#), consulted 14.xi.2025).
- Hinojosa J., Dapporto L., Brockmann E., Dinca V., Tikhonov V., Grishin N., Lukthanov V. & Vila R. 2020. Overlooked cryptic diversity in *Muschampia* (Lepidoptera: Hesperidae) adds two species to the European butterfly fauna. — *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*. 193(3): 847-859. doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa171

- Jakšić P., 1993. The M. Rogulja collection of Rhopalocera (Lepidoptera) from the former state of Yugoslavia. — *Entomologist's Gazette* 44: 85-99. ([url](#))
- Jakšić P. 2003. *Red Data Book of Serbian Butterflies*. — Institute for Nature Conservation of Serbia, Beograd. 198 p. [In Serbian, English summary]
- Jakšić P. 2022. *The First Catalogue of Moth and Butterfly Fauna of Serbia*. — Institute for Biological Research „Siniša Stanković“, Belgrade: 1–1470. ([url](#))
- Jakšić P. 2025. *The Butterflies and Skippers of the Kosovo and Metohija, Republic of Serbia. A Faunal and Ecological study*. — Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković" – National Institute of Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, 277 p. ([url](#)) [In Serbian, English summary]
- Jakšić P. & Đurić M. (2007) 2008. Srpski nazivi dnevnih leptira (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea i Papilionoidea). (Serbian Names for Butterflies). — *Proceeding of the 9th Symposium of flora of Southeastern Serbia and Neighbouring Regions* 231-237. ([url](#))
- Jakšić P., Nahirnić A. & Petrović S. 2013. Compendium of Serbian Butterflies with vernacular names. — *Bulletin of the Natural History Museum* 6: 75-88. ([url](#))
- Jakšić P. & Pešić B. 1995. The distribution of certain *Erebia* species in Serbia (Lepidoptera, Satyridae). — *Univerzitetska misao, prirodne nauke* 2(1): 23-26. ([url](#))
- Krivošej Z. 2013. *Flora of Mount Grmija near Priština*. — Univerzitet u Prištini sa sedištem u Kosovskoj Mitrovici. 190 p. [In Serbian, English summary]
- Krpač V., Darcemont C., Krpač M., Lemonnier-Darcemont M. & Abdija, X. 2021. *Butterflies of the Šar Mountains in the Republic of North Macedonia*. — Edition GEEM – Cannes (06) – France. 254 p.
- Kudrna O., Pennerstorfer J. & Lux K. 2015. *Distribution Atlas of European Butterflies and Skippers*. – Wissenschaftlichen Verlag – Peks, 632 p.
- Lelo S. 2008. *Dnevni leptiri Bosne i Hercegovine (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea i Hesperioidea). Ključ za determinaciju vrsta sa osnovnim monografskim podacima*. — Prirodno-matematički fakultet Univerziteta u Sarajevu. Sarajevo. 333 p.
- Lorković Z. 1930-31. Verwandtschaftliche Beziehungen in der *morsei-major-sinapis* Gruppe des Gen. *Leptidia*. — *Zeitschrift des Österr. Entomologen-Vereines* 15(6): 61-67; 15(9): 85-88; 95-100, 109-111; 15(12): 113-118; 16(2): 9-13, 37-39, 45-48. ([url](#))
- Lorković Z. 1953a. Specifička, semispecifička i rasna diferencijacija kod *Erebia tyndarus* Esp. I. Novi alopatrijski oblici vrste *Erebia tyndarus* Esp. analiza njihovih srodstvenih i sistematskih odnosa. — *Rad Jugo slavenske akademije znanosti i umjetnosti* 294(5): 269-313. ([url](#))
- Lorković Z. 1953b. Specifička, semispecifička i rasna diferencijacija kod *Erebia tyndarus* Esp. II. Stupanj diferencijacije i srodstveni odnosi pirinejskih, alpskih i balkanskih forma. — *Rad Jugoslavenske Akademije znanosti i umjetnosti* 294(5): 315-358. ([url](#))
- Lorković Z. 1954. Spezifische, semispezifische und rassische Differenzierung bei *Erebia tyndarus* Esp. I. Drei neue Allopatrische formen von *Erebia tyndarus* Esp. und der grad ihrer fortpflanzungs isolation. — *Travaux de l'institut de biologie experimental de l'Academie Yougoslave* 12, Bull. int. 10: 163-192.
- Milojković S., Vujić M., Djurić M. & Tot I., 2021. Geranium bronze, *Cacyreus marshalli* Butler, 1897 – new butterfly species for fauna of Serbia (Papilionoidea: Lycaenidae). [Pelargonijev bakrenček, *Cacyreus marshalli* Butler, 1897 – nova vrsta metulja v favni Srbije (Papilionoidea: Lycaenidae)]. — *Acta Entomologica Slovenica* 29(1): 121-124. ([url](#)) [Slovenian summary]
- Ocokoljić M. 1994. Cyclic variation of droughty and watery periods in Serbia. — *Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Geographical Institute "Jovan Cvijić"* Vol. 41: 1–110. ([url](#)) [In Serbian, English summary]
- Popović M. and Verovnik R. 2018. Revised checklist of the butterflies of Serbia (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). — *Zootaxa* 4438(3): 501-527. ([url](#))
- Reljefna mapa Srbije*. — Serbiemap.Net 2009-2021. ([url](#), consulted 18.xi.2025)
- Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. 2025a. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. 2025b. A systematic and synonymic list of the Papilionidae of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea) – Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera. — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(3): 17-56. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17152543

Tot I., Đurić M., Vujić M. & Miljević, M. 2022. *Butterflies of Pčinja Valley*. — Srpska pravoslavna crkva, Eparhija Vranjska, Vranje i HabiProt, 140 p. [In Serbian and English]

van Nieukerken E., Kaila L., Kitching I., Kristensen N., Lees D., Minet J., Mitter C., Mutanen M., Regier J., Simonsen T., Wahlberg N., Yen S., Zahiri R., Adamski D., Baixeras J., Bartsch D., Bengtsson B., Brown J., Bucheli S., Davis D., de Prins J., de Prins W., Epstein M., Gentili-Poole P., Gielis C., Hättenschwiler P., Hausmann A., Holloway J., Kallies A., Karsholt O., Kawahara A., Koster S., Kozlov M., Lafontaine J., Lamas G., Landry J., Lee S., Nuss M., Park K., Penz C., Rota J., Schintlmeister A., Schmidt B., Sohn J., Solis M., Tarmann G., Warren A., Weller S., Yakovlev R., Zolotuhin V. & Zwick A. 2011. Order Lepidoptera Linnaeus, 1758. *In*: Zhang, Z.-Q. (Ed.) Animal biodiversity: An outline of higher-level classification and survey of taxonomic richness — *Zootaxa* 3148(1), 212–221. ([url](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.2011.04601.x))

Van Swaay C., Warren M., Ellis S., Clay J., Bellotto V., Allen D. & Trottet A. 2025. *Measuring the pulse of European biodiversity. European Red List of Butterflies*. — Brussels, Belgium: European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2779/935927>

Vukajlović N., Reljić K., Kostić M., & Vojnović, B. 2025. The Southern Swallowtail, *Papilio alexanor* Esper, 1800 (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae) – new butterfly species for the fauna of Serbia. — *Kragujevac Journal of Science* 47(1): 111–119. ([url](https://doi.org/10.2478/kjs-2025-0001))

Zečević M. 1996. *Pregled faune leptira Srbije*. — Institut za istraživanja u poljoprivredi Srbija, Beograd. 157 p.

Zečević M. & Radovanović S., 1974. Leptiri Timočke Krajine (makrolepidoptera). Prilog poznavanju faune leptirova Srbije. — Zavod za poljoprivredu Zaječar i Novinska ustanova Timok Zaječar, 1–185.. [In Serbian, German summary]

Živojinović, S. 1950. Fauna insekata šumske domene Majdanpeka. (Le Faune des Insectes du Domaine forestier de Majdanpek). — *Srpska akademija nauka CLX, Instit. za ekologiju i biogeografiju* 2: 1–262. [In Serbian, French summary]

A systematic and synonymic list of the HesperIIDae of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

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Abstract

A systematic and synonymic list of the HesperIIDae butterflies of the Western Palearctic is presented, with all names hyperlinked to their original descriptions. The work covers taxonomic hierarchy from family to species level, incorporating historical synonyms, typification details, and bibliographic references, providing a comprehensive and navigable tool for lepidopterists and taxonomists.

Key words

HesperIIDae — Papilionoidea — Lepidoptera — Western Palearctic — taxonomy — nomenclature — synonymy — systematic catalogue — type species — original descriptions — type locality — butterfly classification — historical entomology.

Introduction

The family HesperIIDae comprises groups of species with a remarkably similar habitus, making species identification often challenging. Identification frequently requires examination of the genitalia (e.g., in the genus *Pyrgus*), and in some cases genetic analysis is necessary, for instance to distinguish *Spialia rosae* Hernández-Roldán et al., 2016.

Research on species within this family has long been neglected due to these identification difficulties. Whether owing to scarce material or simple oversight, early authors frequently confused species or grouped several taxa under a single name, resulting in a chaotic classification of the group. Linnaeus described only three species for the European fauna, and his successors made little progress. It was not until Rambur (1839), who described seven new *Pyrgus* species in the same publication, that a coherent outline of the European HesperIIDae fauna began to emerge.

HesperIIDae were traditionally assigned to the superfamily Hesperioidea. The reclassification of the family within Papilionoidea was proposed following significant advances in molecular phylogenetics over the past two decades, as reported by Warren *et al.* (2009) and subsequent studies.

For the Western Palearctic fauna, the implications of these studies remain limited, yet they can occasionally prompt substantial reorganisation within certain groups, such as *Carcharodus*. It is therefore crucial to monitor the current literature closely and to integrate these findings into the systematics of Western Palearctic species.

Regularly updating a comprehensive systematic and synonymic reference list is therefore essential. A dynamic, continuously maintained list offers clear advantages over fixed, paper-based publications, which cannot be revised once issued and may become outdated relatively quickly as new taxonomic findings emerge.

Family

HesperIIDae Latreille, 1809

[ICZN] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187](#), [207](#).

TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

[JS] Diorthosia Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).

TG: *Diorthosus* Rafinesque, 1815.

[RJ] Erynnidae Hampson, 1918. Novit. Zool. 25: [386](#).

TG: *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801 ; name rejected by ICZN – Case 3749, Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 75(1): 130-134.

- [JH] Hesperidae Westwood, 1840. *Introd. Modern Class. Ins.* 2: [360](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [NN] Urbicolae (Fabr.) Scudder, 1872. *Report Peabody Acad. Sci.* 1872: [46](#).
TG: *Urbicola* Linnaeus, 1758.
- [ICZN] Hesperidae Latreille, 1809. In *Opinion 1240 (ICZN, 1983. Bull. Zool. Nomencl.* 40(1): [27-28](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

Subfamily

Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925

- [ORIG] Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. *Erde* 13: [506](#), [546](#).
TG: *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806.
- [IN] Eumesiidae Felder & Felder, [1867]. *Reise Öst. Fregatte Novara, Zool.* 2(2): 504 (invalid by ICZN, opinion 1669).
TG: *Eumesia* Felder & Felder, [1867] (invalid by ICZN, opinion 1669).
- [?] Cyclopidinae Speyer, 1879. *Entomol. Ztg.* 40(10-12): [486](#).
TG: *Cyclopides* Hübner, [1819] (= *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806).
- [JS] Carterocephalini Orfila, 1949. *Acta Zool. Lilloana* 8: 584.
TG: *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1852.

Tribe

Heteropterini Aurivillius, 1925

- [ORIG] Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. *Erde* 13: [506](#), [546](#).
TG: *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806.
- [JS] Carterocephalini Orfila, 1949. *Acta Zool. Lilloana* 8: 584.
TG: *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1853.

Genus

Heteropterus Duméril, 1806

- [ORIG] *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806. *Zool. analyt.*: [271](#).
TS: *Papilio aracinthus* Fabricius, 1777 (= *P. morpheus* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1934. *Gen. names Holarct. Butt.* 1: 167.
- [JS] *Cyclopides* Hübner, [1819]. *Verz. Bekannt. Schmett.* (7): [111](#).
TS: *Papilio steropes* [D. & Schiff.], 1775 (= *P. morpheus* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Butler, 1870. *Entomol. Month. Mag.* 2: [96](#).

Heteropterus morpheus (Pallas, 1771)

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebeius urbicola) morpheus* Pallas, 1771. *Reise verschied. Prov. russ. Reichs* 1: [471](#).
TL: Samara region (Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) speculum* Rottemburg, 1775. *Naturforscher* 6: [31](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) steropes* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. *Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.*: [160](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).

- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) aracinthus* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [271-272](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Papilio speculifer* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [246](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus aniensis* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(20): [82](#).
TL: Monti Sabini (C Italy).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* race *minutus* Lempke, 1936. Tijdschr. Entomol. 79(3-4): [310](#).
TL: Maaseyck (NE Belgium).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* var. *aquitainensis* Pionneau, 1938. Misc. Entomol. 39(6): [50](#).
TL: Bois de Pessac (SW France).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* race *vasconiae* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 327.
TL: Biarritz (SW France).
- [IFS] *Heteropterus morpheus* f.[=ab.] *maculata* Schwingenschuss, 1952. Z. Wien. Entomol. Ges. 37: [131](#).
TL: Herzogenburg (Austria).
- [IFS] *Heteropterus morpheus* f.[=ab.] *luxurians* Lempke, 1953. Tijdschr. Entomol. 96(4): [251](#).
TL: Empe (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus post-morpheus* Floriani, 1968. Boll. Soc. Entomol. It. 98: 118.
TL: Merlino (Lombardia, N Italy).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* ssp. *stangellaieri* Aitsleitner & Gros, 2019. Entomofauna 40: [300](#), [Abb. 1-2](#).
TL: Val Cellina, Claut-Contron (Pordenone prov., NE Italy).

Genus

Carterocephalus Lederer, 1853

- [ORIG] *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1852. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2(Abhandl.): [26](#).
TS: *Papilio paniscus* Fabricius, 1775 (= *P. palaemon* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci 10: [134](#).
- [JS] *Aubertia* Oberthür, 1896. Étud. entomol. 20: [40](#).
TS: *Aubertia dulcis* Oberthür, 1896 (= *C. christophi* Gr.-Grsh., 1891) by subsequent designation by Lindsey, 1925. Ann. entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [79](#).
- [JS] *Pamphilida* Lindsey, 1925. Ann. entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [95](#).
TS: *Papilio palaemon* Pallas, 1771 by original designation.

Carterocephalus silvicola (Meigen, [1829])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia silvicola* Meigen, [1829]. Syst. Besch. eur. Schmett. 2: [65-66](#), [pl. 55](#), [fig. 7a-d](#).
TL: Braunschweig (Lower Saxony, Germany).
- [JH] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) silvius* Knoch, 1781. Beitr. Insektengesch. 1: [71-73](#), [pl. 5](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany) ; nec *Papilio sylvius* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [77](#).

Carterocephalus palaemon Pallas, 1771

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebejus urbicola) palaemon* Pallas, 1771. Reise verschied. Prov. russ. Reichs 1: [471](#).
TL: Akhtushka river (Samara obl., Russian Federation).

- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) paniscus* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [531](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) brontes* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [160](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JS] *Carterocephalus palaemon* var. *albiguttata* Christoph, 1893. Dt. entomol. Z. 6(1): [87-88](#).
TL: Vilui, Irkut, Guberli, Ural merid. (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon* var. *freyi* Hellweger, 1911. Jahresb. Privat-Gymn. Brixen 36: 71.
TL: Wetterstein, Haller Salzberg (Austria).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon silvioides* Muller, 1920. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 70: (52).
TL: Rekawinkel (Austria).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon* ssp. *borealis* Lingonblad, 1945. Notulae Entomol. 24: [71-75, fig.](#)
TL: Vasa (Ostrobothnia prov. Finland).
- [JS] *Carterocephalus palaemon* ssp. *tollii* Krzywicki, 1967. Ann. zool., Warsz. 25(1): 119-121, 150-152, pl. 28, fig. 1-23, pl. 29, fig. 11-12.
TL: Puszcza Białowieska (Poland).
- [JH] *Carterocephalus palaemon* ssp. *sarahe* Gastón Ortíz & Gómez Bustillo, 1974. SHILAP 3(9): [64-66, fig.](#)
TL: Peña de Orduña (Vizcaya prov., Spain).

Subfamily

Hesperiinae Latreille, 1809

- [ORIG] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187, 207](#).
TS: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JS] Pamphilinae Butler, 1871. Entomol. Monthly Mag. 7: [56](#).
TS: *Pamphila* Fabricius 1807.
- [ICZN] Hesperidae Latreille, 1809. In Opinion 1240 (ICZN, 1983. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 40(1): [27-28](#).
TS: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

Tribe

Baorini Doherty, 1886

- [ORIG] Baorinae Doherty, 1886. J. Asiat. Soc. Bengal. 55(2): [107, 111](#).
TG: *Baoris* Moore, 1881.
- [JS] Gegenini Chou, 1994. Zhongguo die lei zhi 1: 14, 88.
TG: *Gegenes* Hübner, [1819].
- [JS] Parnarini Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [102, 110](#).
TG: *Parnara* Moore, [1881].
- [JS] Parnarina Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [110](#).
TG: *Parnara* Moore, [1881].
- [JS] Itonina Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [110](#).
TG: *Iton* Nicéville, 1895.

Genus

Pelopidas Walker, 1870

[ORIG] *Pelopidas* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56](#).

TS: *Pelopidas midea* Walker, 1870 by monotypy.

[JS] *Chapra* Moore, [1881]. Lepid. Ceylon 1(4): [169](#).

TS: *Hesperia mathias* Fabricius, 1798 by original designation.

Pelopidas thrax (Hübner, [1821])

[ORIG] *Gegenes thrax* Hübner, [1821]. Samml. exot. Schmett. 2: [pl. \[150\], fig. 1-4](#).

TL: Syria (?).

[JS] *Pelopidas midea* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56](#).

TL: Cairo (Egypt).

Genus

Borbo Evans, 1949

[ORIG] *Borbo* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [44](#), [436](#).

TS: *Hesperia borbonica* Boisduval, 1833 by original designation.

Borbo borbonica (Boisduval, 1833)

[ORIG] *Hesperia borbonica* Boisduval, 1833. Nouv. Ann. Mus. Hist. nat. 2(2): [213-214](#).

TL: Réunion (Overseas department, France).

[JS] *Hesperia zelleri* Lederer, 1855. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 5(Abhandl.): [194](#).

TL: Syria.

[JS] *Pamphila borbonica holli* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 4: [363-365](#).

TL: Hussein Dey (Algeria).

[NN] *Borbo zelleri tarraconensis* Meliá & Gómez-Bustillo, 1974. Marip. Peníns. Ibér. 2: 31.

TL: Amposta (Tarragona prov., NE Spain).

Genus

Gegenes Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Gegenes* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [107](#).

TL: *Papilio pumilio* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804 by subsequent designation by Opinion 827 (ICZN, 1967. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 24 : 226-227).

[JS] *Philoodus* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 308.

Hesperia nostradamus Fabricius, 1793 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci 10: [248](#).

Gegenes pumilio (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804)

[ORIG] *Papilio pumilio* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [202](#).

TL: Amalfi (Salerno prov., Italy).

[JH] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) pygmaeus* Cyrillo, [1791]. Entomol. Neapol.: [pl. 5, fig. 5](#).

TL: Naples (S Italy) ; *nec* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [536](#).

- [JS] *Hesperia aetna* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [35](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Philoodus lefebvrei* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 308.
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Gegenes pumilio* ssp. *balearica* Fernández Vidal, 1987. SHILAP 15(60): [346-347, fig.](#)
TL: Bunyola (Mallorca, Islas Baleares, Spain).

Gegenes nostradamus (Fabricius, 1793)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia nostradamus* Fabricius, 1793. Entomol. Syst. 3(1): [328-329](#).
TL: NW Africa (Algeria).
- [JS] *Pamphila proclea* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5: [56](#).
TL: Cairo (Egypt).
- [JS] *Gegenes nostradamus* race *pumilionimina* Verity, 1931. Boll. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 63(6-7): 111.
TL: Viareggio, Lucca (Tuscany, Italy).

Tribe

Hesperiini Latreille, 1809

- [ORIG] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187, 207](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JH] Hesperidae Westwood, 1840. Introd. Modern Class. Ins. 2: [360](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JS] Thymelicinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [90](#).
TG: *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Ochlodes Scudder, 1872

- [ORIG] *Ochlodes* Scudder, 1872. Report Peabody Acad. Sci. 1872: [57](#).
TL: *Hesperia nemorum* Boisduval, 1852 (= *Hesperia agricola* Boisduval, 1852) by original description.

Ochlodes sylvanus (Esper, 1777)

- [ORIG] *Papilio* (*Plebeius Urbicola*) *sylvanus* Esper, 1777. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): pl. 36 (suppl. 12), fig. 1 ; [1779]: [343](#).
TL: Franconia (N Bavaria, Germany) ; see Opinion 1944 (ICZN, 2000. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 57(1): [56-57](#)).
- [JH] *Papilio* (*Plebeius Urbicola*) *melicerta* Bergsträsser, 1780. Nom. Ins. 4: [38, pl. 90, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Drury, 1773. Illustr. Nat. Hist. 2: [34, pl. 19, fig. 3-4, index \[1\]](#).
- [JS] [*Hesperia*] *anatolica* Plötz, 1883. Entomol. Ztg. 44: [219](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Hesperia hyrcana* Christoph, 1893. Dt. Entomol. Z. 6(1): [87](#).
TL: Lenkoran (Azerbaijan), Astrabad (Iran).
- [JS] *Augiades faunus* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [36-38, pl. 6, fig. 5, 9](#).
TL: Gavarnie (France).

- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* var. *norvegica* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [135](#).
TL: Saeterstoen (Norway).
- [JS] *Adopaea sylvanus alpina* Hoffmann & Klos, 1914. Mitt. Naturwiss. Ver. Steiermark 50: [314](#).
TL: Krieglach (Austria).
- [JS] *Augiades (Erynnis) sylvanus* f. *sylvanellus* Turati, 1915. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 53(3-4): 603.
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* race *septentrionalis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: England.
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus taurica* Gaede, 1931. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1(suppl.): [322](#), pl. 16k, fig. [10-11].
TL: England.
- [JS] *Ochlodes venata alexandra* Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(5): [99](#), [200](#).
TL: Nom. nov. pro *Papilio sylvanus*, Esper, 1777 (invalid, homonym of *Papilio sylvanus*, Drury, 1773) ; see Opinion [1944](#) (ICZN, 2000).
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus esperi* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13](#).
TL: Nom. nov. pro *Papilio sylvanus*, Esper, 1777 (invalid, homonym of *Papilio sylvanus*, Drury, 1773) ; see Opinion [1944](#) (ICZN, 2000).
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* ssp. *nicaeensis* Praviel, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 324.
TL: Alpes-Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum* race *concoulensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 41.
TL: Gard (France).
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum* f. *pseudonicaeense* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schweiz Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [373](#).
TL: S Tessin, ... (Switzerland)
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum hesperodoron* Kauffmann, 1956. Entomol. Z. 66(5): 54.
TL: Europe.

Genus

Hesperia Fabricius, 1793

- [ORIG] *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793. Entomol. Syst. 3(1): [258](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. 1816: [200-201](#).
- [JS] *Pamphila* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Westwood, 1840. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Diorthosus* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Hesperia* Cuvier, 1800).
- [JS] *Phidias* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Pamphila* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JH] *Symmachia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10(6): [82](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793) ; nec *Symmachia* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [25-26](#).
- [JS] *Ocytes* Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [76](#).
TS: *Hesperia metea* Scudder, 1863 by original designation.
- [JS] *Anthomaster* Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [78](#).
TS: *Hesperia leonardus* Harris, 1862 by original designation.
- [JS] *Urbicola* (Linnaeus): Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8(1): [84](#).

TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

Hesperia comma (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebejus urbicola) comma* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio virgula* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [31](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* var. *catena* Staudinger, 1861. Entomol. Ztg. 22: [357](#).
TL: Lappland (Sweden).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* var. *alpina* Harcourt-Bath, 1896. Entomologist 29(392): [21](#).
TL: Wengern-Scheideck Pass (Bern, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Augiades comma* var. *pallida* Staudinger, 1901. In Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [92](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Augiades comma* var. *apennina* Rostagno, 1911. In: Rostagno & Zapelloni, Boll. Soc. Zool. Ital. (2)12(1-4): [10-11](#).
TL: Lazio (C Italy).
- [JS] *Augiades benuncas* Oberthür, 1912. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1912(16): [349-351](#).
TL: Lambèse (Algeria).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *aurata* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7/8): [107](#).
TL: Abetone (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *orae* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7/8): [107](#).
TL: Pertusola, Gulf of Spezia (Liguria, Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *galliaemeridiei* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [124-125](#).
TL: Nîmes (Gard, S France).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *hibera* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragon, Spain).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *alpapennina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125](#).
TL: Bolognola, Mts Sibillini (Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *alpiumflava* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125-126](#).
TL: Bolzano (NE Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *macrocomma* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [126-127](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *superalpina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [127](#).
TL: Stelvio, Vallée de Bornio (N Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *altralpina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [127](#).
TL: Haut de la route du Stelvio, Sulden, Ortler (N Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* race *hemipallida* Verity, 1940. Farf. Dirne Ital. 1: 116, pl. 4, fig. 66-69.
TL: Madonie (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* race *maroccana* Picard, 1950. Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Maroc 28: [129-130](#).
TL: Afraou des Beni Abdallah (Moyen Atlas, Morocco).

Genus

Thymelicus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [113](#).

TG: *Papilio actaeon* Esper (= *Papilio acteon* Rott., 1775) by subsequent designation by Butler, 1870. Entomol. Month. Mag. 7: [94](#).

[JS] *Adopoea* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [81](#).

TG: *Papilio linea* Müller, 1766 (= *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761) by monotypy.

[JS] *Pelion* Kirby, 1858. List Brit. Rhop.: [\[3\]](#).

TG: *Papilio linea* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 (= *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761) by original designation.

[IS] *Thymelinus* Stephens, [1835]. Illustr. Brit. Entomol. 4: [405](#).

Incorrect subsequent spelling of *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819].

Thymelicus christi Rebel, 1894

[ORIG] *Thymelicus christi* Rebel, 1894. Ann. Naturhist. Hofmus. 9(1): [41-42](#), [pl. 1, fig. 2](#).

TL: Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain).

Thymelicus acteon (Rottemburg, 1775)

[ORIG] *Papilio* (*Plebejus Urbicola*) *acteon* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [30-31](#).

TL: Landsberg an der Warthe, current city of Gorzów Wielkopolski (Lubuskie prov., Poland).

[JH] *Papilio actaeon* [sic] Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 96, fig. 488-490](#), [1806]: [73](#).

Incorrect subsequent spelling of *Papilio acteon* Rottemburg, 1775.

[CN] *Thymelicus actaeon* [sic] Hübner, [1819]. Verz. Bekannt. Schmett.(7): [113](#).

Comb. nov. for *Papilio acteon* Rottemburg, 1775.

[JS] *Thymelicus heydeni* Plötz, 1884. Entomol. Ztg. 45(7-9): [285](#).

TL: Syria [?].

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *virescens* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [118](#).

TL: United Kingdom.

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: Grésy-sur-Aix (Haute-Savoie dep., E France).

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *obsoleta* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: -.

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *extensa* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: Chavoire (Haute-Savoie dep., E France).

[JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *ragusai* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).

TL: Palermo, S. Martino alle Scale (Sicily, S Italy).

[JS] *Thymelicus* (*Adopaea*) *acteon* race *obsoleta* Tutt: Turner, 1920. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 1920(1/2): [206](#).

Stat. nov. for *Thymelicus acteon* ab. *obsoleta* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

[JS] *Thymelicus* (*Adopaea*) *acteon* f. *clara-obsoleta* Turner, 1920. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 1920(1/2): [206](#).

TL: Cyprus.

[JS] *Thymelicus* (*Adopaea*) *acteon* ssp. *phoenix* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [44-45, pl. 5, fig. 6-7](#).

TL: Jemhur-Areya, Beirut (Lebanon).

- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *clara* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 103-104, pl. 4, fig. 36-37.
Stat. rev. for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *aurescens* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 103-104, pl. 4, fig. 36-37.
Stat. rev., replacement name for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *pulchractaeon* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 104, pl. 4, fig. 40-42.
TL: Gran Sasso (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *virescens* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 105, pl. 4, fig. 43-45.
Stat. rev. for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *virescens* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* [sic] ssp. *orana* Evans, 1949. Cat. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [345](#).
TL: Morocco, Algeria.
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *maurus* Picard, 1948. Bull. Soc. Sci. nat. Maroc 28: [126-127](#).
TL: Casablanca (Morocco).

Thymelicus hamza (Oberthür, 1876)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia hamza* Oberthür, 1876. Étud. Entomol. 1: 28-29, pl. 3, fig. 2a-c.
TL: Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Adopaea* (*Thymelicus*) *novissima* Turati, 1921. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 60: [221-225, fig.](#)
TL: Al Fuehat (Libya).

Thymelicus hyrax (Lederer, 1861)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia hyrax* Lederer, 1861. Wiener entomol. Monatschr. 5(5): [149-150, pl. 1, fig. 6](#).
TL: Antioch, current city of Antakya (Hatay prov., Turkey).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *pfeifferi* Bytinski-Salz & Brandt, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [\(2\)-\(3\)](#).
TL: Al Fuehat (Libya).

Thymelicus sylvestris (Poda, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Graz (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio flava* Brünnich, 1763. In: Pontoppidan, Danske Atlas 1: [685, pl. 30, fig.\[2\]](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *Papilio thaumas* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [62-63](#).
TL: Berlin (Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio linea* Müller, 1766. In: Allioni, Misc. Taurin. 3: [192](#).
TL: Turin (Italy).
- [JS] *P[apilio]. flavus* Müller, 1776. Zool. Dan. Prodr.: [115](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *P[apilio]. divaricatus* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [246-247](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Papilio venula* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 131, fig. 666-669](#), 1824: [6](#).
TL: Germany.

- [JS] *Adopaea flava* var. *syriaca* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Syria.
- [IFS] *Adopaea flava* ab. *iberica* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Canales, Moncayo, Bejar, ... (Spain).
- [IFS] *Adopaea flava* ab. *major* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Villach, ... (Austria).
- [SR] *Adopaea flava* race *iberica* Verity, 1920. Boll. Lab. Zool. Portici 14: [43](#).
Stat rev. for *Adopaea flava* ab. *iberica* Tutt, 1905..
- [NN] *Adopaea flava* race *macta* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [104](#).
Nom. nov. and Stat. rev. for *Adopaea flava* ab. *major* Tutt, 1905.
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* ssp. *fulminans* Rebel & Zerny, [1932]. Denkschr. Akad. Wiss. Wien 103: [83](#), pl. 1, fig. 3-4.
TL: Kula e Lumës (Albania).
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* race *maxima* Verity, 1936. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 48(suppl.): [\(3\)-\(4\)](#).
TL: Thessaloniki (N Greece).
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* var. *werneri* Rebel, 1937. Z. Öst. Entomol. Ver. 22(7): [66](#).
TL: Kifissia (Attica, C Greece).
- [ND] *Thymelicus sylvester* ff. *claricantes* Kauffmann, [1953]. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 47/48: [11](#).
Nom. nud., stat. of 'ff' ?
- [ND] *Thymelicus sylvester* ff. *nigricantes* Kauffmann, [1953]. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 47/48: [11](#).
Nom. nud., stat. of 'ff' ?

Thymelicus lineola (Ochsenheimer, 1808)

- [ORIG] *Papilio lineola* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [230-231](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JH] *Papilio virgula* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 130, fig. 660-663](#), 1824: [5](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [31](#)..
- [JS] *Pamphila ludoviciae* Mabille, 1883. Ann. Soc. entomol. Belg. 27(suppl.): [lxviii-lxix](#).
TL: Murat (Auvergnés, France), Pyrénées (France).
- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* var. *semicolon* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 5(2): [282](#).
TL: Lambèse (Algeria).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Larche (SE France).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *major* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Wolfsberg (Austria).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *major-clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Tragacete (Spain).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *intermedia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Macugnaga (N Italy).
- [SR] *Thymelicus lineola* ssp. *major-clara* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [42-43](#).
Stat. rev. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *major-clara* Tutt, 1906.

- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* f. *diluta* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [43](#).
TL: Shar Deresy (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* f.[var.] *hemmingi* Romei, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(9): [127](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ssp. *pseudothaumas* Zerny, 1927. Eos 3(3): [342](#).
TL: Losilla (Teruel prov., Spain).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ssp. *melissus* Zerny, 1932. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 46(4): 188.
TL: N Lebanon.
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* f. *fornax* Hemming, 1934. Entomologist 67(859): 198.
TL: Palestine.
- [JS] *Adopaea lineola* race *italamixta* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 96, pl. 3, fig. 96-104.
TL: Sesto Fiorentino (Toscana, Italy).
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *clara* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 96-97.
Stat. rev. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *intermedia* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 98, pl. 4, fig. 8-13.
Stat. nov. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *intermedia* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *major* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 98, pl. 4, fig. 14-19.
Stat. nov. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *major* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* race *ifranensis* Picard, 1948. Bull. Soc. Sci. nat. Maroc 28: [128-129](#).
TL: Ifrane (Maroc).

Subfamily

Pyrginae Burmeister, 1878

- [ORIG] Pyrgidae Burmeister, 1878. Descr. phys. Rép. Argentine 5: [245-246](#).
TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].
- [SS] Antigonini Mabile, 1878. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg. 21: [28, nota](#).
TG: *Antigonus* Hübner, [1819].
- [JS] Pyrginae Speyer, 1879. Entomol. Ztg. 40: [484](#).
TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Carcharodini Verity, 1940

- [ORIG] Carcharodidi Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 10.
TG: *Carcharodus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Spialia Swinhoe, [1912]

- [ORIG] *Spialia* Swinhoe, [1912]. In: Moore, Lepid. ind. 10: [99](#).
TS: *Hesperia galba* Fabricius, 1793 by original designation.

- [JH] *Powellia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [218](#).
nec Maskell, 1879. Trans. Proc. New Zeal. Inst. 11: [223](#).
TS: *Papilio sao* Hübner, 1800 (= *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804) by original designation.
- [RN] *Spialia* sect. *Neospialia* Koçak, 1989. Priamus 5(1/2): [67](#).
Replacement name for *Powellia* Tutt, 1906 nec Maskell, 1879.
TS: *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804 by original designation.

Subgenus

Spialia Swinhoe, [1912]

- [ORIG] *Spialia* Swinhoe, [1912]. In: Moore, Lepid. ind. 10: [99](#).
TS: *Hesperia galba* Fabricius, 1793 by original designation.
- [JH] *Powellia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [218](#).
nec Maskell, 1879. Trans. Proc. New Zeal. Inst. 11: [223](#).
TS: *Papilio sao* Hübner, 1800 (= *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804) by original designation.
- [RN] *Spialia* sect. *Neospialia* Koçak, 1989. Priamus 5(1/2): [67](#).
Replacement name for *Powellia* Tutt, 1906 nec Maskell, 1879.
TS: *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804 by original designation.

Spialia (Spialia) ali (Oberthür, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus ali* Oberthür, 1881. Étud. Entomol. 6: [61](#), [pl. 2](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: prov. Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus sao* f. *therapnoides* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. lépid. comp. 4: [385](#), [678](#), [pl. 54](#), [fig. 448](#).
TL: Sebdo (Algeria).

Spialia (Spialia) therapne (Rambur, 1832)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia therapne* Rambur, 1832. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1: [265](#), [pl. 7](#), [fig. 4](#).
TL: Corsica (S France).
- [IFS] *Spialia hibiscae* (eserge *therapne*) f. *retrograda* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia. 1: 80, pl. 3, fig. 75-76.
TL: Valle del Gennargentu (Sardinia, Italy).

Spialia (Spialia) sertorius (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804)

- [ORIG] *Papilio sertorius* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [203](#).
TL: Germany.
- [RJ] *Papilio hibiscae* Hübner, [1793]. Schmett. Lepid. Linn. Eur. Heer: 15.
Papilio hibiscae Hübner, [1793] was placed on the Official Index of Rejected and invalid specific names in Zoology, Name No 980 by Opinion 975 (ICZN, 1971).
- [JH] *Papilio sao* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 93](#), [fig. 471-472](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio sao* Bergsträsser, 1779. Nomencl. Ins. 2: [67](#), [pl. 40](#), [fig. 8-9](#).
- [JS] *Papilio eucrate* Ochsenheimer, [1808]. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [213](#).
TL: Portugal.

- [IFS] *Hesperia sao* var.(gen.II.) *aestiva* Melcón, 1910. Bol. R. Soc. Esp. Hist. Nat. 10: [231](#).
TL: Serrania de Cuenca (Spain).
- [IFS] *Powellia sao* gen.II. *gracilis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: Florence (Italy).
- [SR] *Powellia sao* race *gracilis* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [173-174](#).
TL: Fegana Valley (Tuscany, Italy) ; Stat. rev. for *Powellia sao* gen.II. *gracilis* Verity, 1919 (infrasubspecific).
- [IFS] *Powellia sao* *sao* Gen.II. *parvula* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [173-174](#).
TL: Atzwang (South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Powellia sao* race *guadarramensis* Warren, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [77](#).
TL: La Granja de San Ildefonso (prov. Segovia, C Spain).
- [JS] *owellia sertorius* race *gavarniensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): [139, pl. 49, fig. 6-8](#).
TL: Gavarnie (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, S France).
- [JS] *Powellia sao* race *alioides* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [103](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).

Spialia (Spialia) rosae Hernández-Roldán, Dapporto, Dincă, Vicente & Vila, 2016

- [ORIG] *Spialia rosae* Hernández-Roldán, Dapporto, Dincă, Vicente & Vila, 2016. Molecular Ecology 25(17): 4281.
TL: Puerto de la Ragua (Sierra Nevada, prov. Granada, Spain).

Spialia (Spialia) orbifer (Hübner, [1823])

- [ORIG] *Papilio orbifer* Hübner, [1823]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 161, fig. 803-806](#).
TL: - (Hungary).
- [JS] *Hesperia eucrate* var. *tesselloides* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [154, pl.\(Hesp.\) 2, fig. 10-11](#).
TL: Sicily ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia orbifer* var. *hilaris* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [96](#).
TL: Mardin (SE Turkey).

Subgenus

Platygnathia Picard, [1948]

- [ORIG] *Platygnathia* Picard, [1948]. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 52(8): [132](#).
TS: *Hesperia phlomidis* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845] by original designation.

Spialia (Platygnathia) phlomidis (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia phlomidis* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [153, 164, pl. \(Hesperides\) 2, fig. 8-9](#).
TL: Sea of Marmara (NW Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichtus jason* Oberthür, 1912. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 6: [75-76, pl. 137, fig. 1211](#).
TL: ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichtus phlomidis* ssp. *eupator* Hemming, 1932. Entomologist 65: 182.
TL: Amasia (Turkey).

- [JS] *Spialia phlomidis* ssp. *hermona* Evans, 1957. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (12)9: [750](#).
TL: Mt. Hermon (Syria).
- [JS] *Spialia phlomidis* ssp. *kiki* Higgins, 1974. J. Entomol. (B)43(1): [83-87, fig.](#)
TL: Cedar Mt. (Lebanon).

Spialia (Platynathia) doris (Walker, 1870)

- [ORIG] *Nisoniades doris* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56-57](#).
TL: Tajora (Bab-el-Mandeb Strait, Djibouti).
- [JS] *Pyrgus evanidus* var. *adenensis* Butler, 1884. Proc. Zool. Soc. London 1884: [493](#).
TL: ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia amenophis* Reverdin 1914. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3: 55, pl. 3, fig. 5-11.
TL: Heliopolis (Egypt).
- [JS] *Spialia doris* ssp. *daphne* Evans, 1949. Cat. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr.: [177](#).
TL: Ziz Valley (High Atlas, Morocco).

Genus

Favria Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Favria* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Hesperia cribrellum* Eversmann, 1841 by original designation.

Favria cribrellum (Eversmann, 1841)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cribrellum* Eversmann, 1841. Bull. Soc. imp. nat. Mosc. 14(1): [25-27](#).
TL: Orenburg (S Ural, Volga distr., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Muschampia cribrellum* ssp. *inexpectata* Davkov & Mérit, 2018. Lépidoptères 27(69): [3-7, fig.](#)
TL: Mt. Olympus (Greece).

Genus

Muschampia Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Muschampia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Papilio proto* Esper, 1830 by original designation.

Subgenus

Muschampia Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Muschampia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Papilio proto* Esper, 1830 by original designation.
- [JS] *Tuttia* Warren, 1926. Trans. R. entomol. Soc. Lond. 74: [15](#).
TS: *Papilio tessellum* Hübner, 1800 by original designation.

Muschampia (Muschampia) tessellum (Hübner, [1803])

- [ORIG] *Papilio tessellum* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 93, fig. 469-470](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Papilio mazzola* Ochsenheimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [158](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Papilio hibisci* (Boeber): Ochsenheimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [158](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Hesperia nomas* Lederer, 1855. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 5: [193, pl. 1, fig. 7](#).
TL: Beyrout (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Muschampia tessellum* ssp. *tersa* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [181](#).
TL: Kurdistan (Iraq).

Muschampia (Muschampia) proto (Esper, [1808])

- [ORIG] *Papilio proto* Esper, [1808]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 2: [pl. 123 \(cont. 78\), fig. 5-6](#), [1830]: [32-33](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Papilio proto* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [210](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Hesperia proto* race *aragonensis* Sagarra, 1924. Buttl. Inst. catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [203-204](#).
TL: Albarracín (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* race *nigrita* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54-55](#).
TL: Cuenca (prov. Cuenca, Spain).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* race *fulvosatura* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [55](#).
TL: Sebdou (Algeria).
- [JH] *Muschampia proto* race *gigas* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [55](#).
TL: Azrou (Morocco).
- [NN] *Sloperia proto* race *macroproto* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entoml. Fr. 1928(8): [141](#).
Nom. nov. pro *Muschampia proto gigas* Verity, 1925 nec *Pyrgus gigas* Bremer, 1864. Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. St.-Pétersb. (8)8(1): [96, pl. 8, fig. 3](#).
- [JS] *Sloperia proto* f. *williamsi* Querci, 1932. Treb. Mus. Ciènc. Nat. Barc. 14: [248](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Muschampia proto evansi* Bryk, 1940. Ark. Zool. 32A(22): 25, pl. 4, fig. 23.
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* ssp. *lambesa* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [183](#).
TL: Lambese (NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* ssp. *chelalae* Gómez Bustillo, 1973. SHILAP Revta. lepid. 1(1-2): [32-33, pl. \[1\], fig. 7](#).
TL: Campo Real (prov. Madrid, C Spain).

Muschampia (Muschampia) proteides (Wagner, 1929)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *proteides* Wagner, 1929. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 19(1): [Erklärung zu Tafel II, pl. 2, fig. 26](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).

- [JS] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *lycaonius* Wagner, 1929. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 19(2-4): [64](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichthus hieromax* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [291-293, pl. 15, fig. 23, pl. 16, fig. 50](#).
TL: W Ajlun (Jordan).
- [JS] *Sloperia sovietica* Sichel, 1964. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 43: [166-171, fig.](#)
TL: Sarepta (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Muschampia proteides* ssp. *stepporum* Benyamini & Avni, 2001. Linneana Belg. 18(1): [45-54, fig.](#)
TL: Ma'ale Efraim (Palestine).

Muschampia (Muschampia) alta (Schwingenschuss, 1942)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *alta* Schwingenschuss, 1942. Z. Wien. Entomol.-Ver. 27(8): [182](#).
TL: Taormina (Messina prov., Sicily, Italy).

Muschampia (Muschampia) mohammed (Oberthür, 1887)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus mohammed* Oberthür, 1887. Bull. séances bibliogr. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1887: [xlvi-xlix](#).
TL: Sebdo (Tlemcen prov., Algeria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus ahmed* Oberthür, 1912. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 6: [108, 342, pl. 140, fig. 1259-1260](#).
TL: Lambèse (NE Algeria)
- [JS] *Hesperia caid* Le Cerf, 1923. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 28(15): [198](#).
TL: Oulmès (prov. Khemisset, Morocco).

Muschampia (Muschampia) leuzeae (Oberthür, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus leuzeae* Oberthür, 1881. Étud. Entomol. 6: [60, pl. 3, fig. 10](#).
TL: Mascara (Algeria).

Subgenus

Reverdinus Ragusa, [1919]

- [ORIG] *Reverdinus* Ragusa, [1919]. Nat. Sicil. 23(7-12): [172-173](#).
TS: *Papilio altheae* Hübner, 1800 by subsequent designation by Lindsey, 1925. Ann. Entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [100](#).
- [JS] *Lavatheria* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 11, 22.
TS: *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, 1783 by original designation.

Muschampia (Reverdinus) floccifera (Zeller, 1847)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia floccifera* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [286-287](#).
TL: Syracuse (Sicily, Italy).
- [RJ] *Papilio alchymillae* Hübner, [1793]. Schmett. Lepid. Linn. Heer: 15.
TL: Hanau (Germany) ; The name *Papilio alchymillae* Hübner, [1790-1793] was placed on the Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Species Names in Zoology by ICZN, 1971 - Opinion 975. Bull. 28(5/6): [154](#) (Name No 979).
- [JH] *Papilio altheae* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 90, fig. 452-453](#), [1806]: [63](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec*, incorrect spelling for *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783]: [149](#) (= *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1759).

- [JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) altheae* race *australiformis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [NN] *Carcharodus imperator* Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3: 99.
Nom. nov. pro *Papilio altheae* Hübner, [1803], nec *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783].
- [JS] *Spilothyrsus altheae* race *siccior* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [\(5\)](#).
TL: Terme di Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus floccifera* var. *rungsi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 27.
TL: Gard (S France).
- [JS] *Carcharodus floccifera* race *pyrenaicus* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 11(15-16): 325.
TL: Gègre (Hautes-Pyrénées, France).
- [JS] *Reverdinus floccifer* ssp. *habida* Kauffmann, 1955. Mitt. schweiz. Entoml. Ges. 28(3): [288-290, fig. 1-8](#).
TL: Bab el Taza (Morocco).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) orientalis (Reverdin, 1913)

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus orientalis* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 2(1-4): [225, 230-235, pl. 21, fig. 14](#).
TL: Peloponnese (S Greece).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* var. *centralanatolica* Pfeiffer, 1927. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Münch. 17(1-6): [44-45](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [IFS] *Spilothyrsus orientalis* gen. II. *postorientalis* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 33(8): [140](#).
TL: Constantinople (= Istanbul, W Turkey).
- [IFS] *Spilothyrsus orientalis* gen. II. *aestatis* Graves, 1928. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 40(5): [77](#).
TL: Constantinople (= Istanbul, W Turkey).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* ssp. *maccabaeus* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [295, pl. 15, fig. 18-19, pl. 16, fig. 45-46](#).
TL: Sukhni, N Zerqa (Jordan).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* ssp. *teberdinus* Devjatkin, 1990. Entomol. Rev. 69(4): [933-935](#).
TL: Teberda (Karachay–Cherkess Rep., Russian Federation).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) stauderi (Reverdin, 1913)

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus stauderi* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 2(1-4): [225, 230-235, pl. 21, fig. 5, 12](#).
TL: El Kantara, El Kroubs (Algeria).
- [JS] *Carcharodus ramses* Reverdin, 1914. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 3: 38, fig.
TL: Maryut (Egypt).
- [JS] *Erynnis barcaeus* Turati, 1927. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 63: [37-41](#), pl. 1, fig. 20-21.
TL: Libya.
- [IFS] *Erynnis stauderi* gen. II *fulvissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43-44](#).
TL: Syria, Turkey.
- [JS] *Erynnis oberthuri* race *ambigua* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43-44](#).
TL: Syria, Turkey.
- [JS] *Erynnis stauderi* f. *obscurata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [44](#).
TL: Algeria.

[JS] *Carcharodus stauderi* ssp. *romeii* Rothschild, 1933. Novit. Zool. 38(2): [323](#).
TL: Ketama (Morocco).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) baeticus (Rambur, [1839])

[ORIG] *Syrichtus baeticus* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(4): [pl. 12, fig. 3-4](#).

TL: Andalusia (S Spain).

[JS] *Pamphila marrubii* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(6): 323.

TL: Andalusia (S Spain).

[JS] *Carcharodus baeticus* race *octodurensis* Oberthür, 1911. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 5(1): [195](#).

TL: Martigny (Valais, Switzerland).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) boeticus* [sic] race *rostagnoi* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).

TL: Oricola, Latium (prov. L'Aquila, C Italy).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) boeticus* [sic] race *oberthueri* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).

TL: Sicily (S Italy).

[JS] *Erynnis marrubii* race *fulvescens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).

TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* gen. I *grisea* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).

TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* gen. III *aegra* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).

TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* f. *viridescens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43](#).

TL: dep. Bouches-du-Rhône ? (S France).

[JS] *Erynnis marrubii* race *fulva* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43](#).

TL: Cuenca (C Spain).

[JS] *Spilothyris marrubii* race *fonti* Sagarra, 1930. Butll. Catal. Hist. Nat. (2)10(7): [118](#).

TL: Horcajo, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) lavatherae (Esper, [1783])

[ORIG] *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, [1783]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [148-149](#), [pl. 82 \(cont. 32\)](#), [fig. 4](#).

TL: France ; Switzerland.

[JH] *Papilio tages* Sulzer, 1776. Gesch. Ins. 1: [146](#), 2: [pl. 19, fig. 6-7](#).

nec Papilio tages Linnaeus, 1758: [485](#).

[JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* var. *rufescens* Oberthür, 1914. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 10: [407-408](#), [pl. 296, fig. 4433](#).

TL: Sebdou, Méchéria (Algeria).

[JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* ssp. *internirufus* Rothschild, 1914. Novit. Zool. 21(4): [311](#).

TL: Ain Sefra, Guelt-es-Stel (C Algeria).

[JS] *Carcharodus tauricus* Reverdin, 1915. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3(2): 103-108, pl. 5, fig. 1-2.

TL: Külek (Turkey).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) lavatherae* race *australior* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).

TL: Tuscany (Italy).

- [JS] *Erynnis lavatherae* race *australissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [41-42](#).
TL: Sebdou (Algeria).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* f. *chlorotes* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(20): [82](#).
TL: Terlan (South Tyrol prov., NE Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* race *nigroboscuroata* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 50(suppl.): [1-3](#).
TL: Skala (N Greece).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* var. *rungsi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 28.
TL: Gard (S France).

Genus

Carcharodus Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett. (7): [110](#).
TS: *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780] by designation by Opinion 181 (ICZN, 1946: [607](#)) and by Opinion 270 (ICZN, 1954: [29](#)).
- [JS] *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835]. Hist. Nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: <http://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/37742#page/523/mode/1up>.
TS: *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780] by designation by Opinion 270 (ICZN, 1954: [29](#)).
- [IS] *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835]. Hist. Nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [419](#).
Incorrect spelling for *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835].

Carcharodus alceae (Esper, [1780])

- [ORIG] *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(2): [4-6](#), [pl. 51](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: Germany.
- [ND] *Papilio fritillarius* Poda, 1761 Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Graz (Austria) ; Nomen dubium.
- [JH] *Hapilio maluae* [sic] Bergsträsser, 1780. Nomencl. Ins. 4: [39-40](#), [pl. 91](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
- [JS] *Papilio malvarum* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [198](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Hesperia malvarum* var. *nostras* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [285-286](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia malvarum* var. *australis* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [285-286](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia gemina* Lederer, 1853. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2: [26](#), [50](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Spilolhyrus alceae* var. *aestiva* Hormuzaki, 1897. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 47: [164](#).
TL: Bukowina (Romania ; Ukraine).
- [JS] *Erynnis alceae* f. *fulvocarens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54](#).
TL: Tenna Valley, Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [IFS] *Erynnis alceae* race *magnaustralis* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7-8): [106](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).

- [JS] *Carcharodus fritillarius* race *claraustralis* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [2](#).
TL: Mount Carmel (Israel).
- [JS] *Carcharodus fritillarius* race *claraminima* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [2](#).
TL: Malatia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Carcharodus alceae* f. *exigua* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 14.
TL: Atina (Lazio, C Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus alceae* var. *corsicus* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 11(15-16): 324.
TL: Corse (S France).

Carcharodus tripolina (Verity, 1925)

- [ORIG] *Erynnis alceae* race *tripolina* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54](#).
TL: Garian plateau, S Tripoli (Libya).

Tribe

Erynnini Brues & Melander, 1932

- [ORIG] Erynninae Brues & Melander, 1932. Bull. Mus. comp. Zool. 73: [235-236](#).
TG: *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801.

Genus

Erynnis Schrank, 1801

- [ORIG] *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [157-160](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [70-71](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, *Mag. Insektenk.* 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* [Illiger], 1807. *Allg.-Lit. Ztg. Halle* 1807(2)(303): [1180](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Astycus* Hübner, 1822. *Syst.-alph. Verz.*: [1](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 200.
- [JS] *Thanaos* Boisduval, [1834]. *Icon. Hist. Lépid. Europ.* 1(23): [240](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: [469](#).

Subgenus

Erynnis Schrank, 1801]

- [ORIG] *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [157-160](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [70-71](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, *Mag. Insektenk.* 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* [Illiger], 1807. *Allg.-Lit. Ztg. Halle* 1807(2)(303): [1180](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).

- [JS] *Astycus* Hübner, 1822. Syst.-alph. Verz.: [1](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 200.
- [JS] *Thanaos* Boisduval, [1834]. *Icon. Hist. Lépid. Europ.* 1(23): [240](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: [469](#).

Erynnis (Erynnis) tages (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
TL: Sweden..
- [JS] *Papilio morio* Scopoli, 1763. Entomol. Carn.: [181-182](#).
TL: Krain (Slovenia).
- [JS] *Papilio geryon* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [31-32](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Thanaos cervantes* Graslin, 1836. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 5: [558-561](#), [pl. 17 B.](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JH] *Hesperia cervantes* Freyer, [1842]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 5(67): [56-57](#), [pl. 417](#), [fig. 3](#).
nec Graslin, 1836..
- [JS] *Hesperia unicolor* Freyer, [1847]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(85): [37](#), [pl. 505 fig. 1](#).
TL: Islands in Greece.
- [IFS] *Nisoniades tages* ab. *clarus* Caradja, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 8: [61](#).
TL: Grumăzești (Romania).
- [JS] *Nisoniades tages* race *subclarus* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [172](#).
TL: Campodazzo, Merano (prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* race *magnatages* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 50(suppl.): [1](#).
TL: Skala (N Greece).
- [SR] *Erynnis tages* race *clarus* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 8-9.
Statut rev. for *Nisoniades tages* ab. *clarus* Caradja, 1895.
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* race *brunnea* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 9.
TL: Torre Pellice (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* ssp. *baynesi* Higgins, 1956. Entomologist 89: 241-242.
TL: The Burren (Ireland).

Subgenus

Hesperopegasus Seven, 2002

- [ORIG] *Hesperopegasus* Seven, 2002. In: Koçak & Kemal, Misc. Pap. CESA 82/85: 27, fig.
TS: *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834] by original designation.
- [JS] *Hallia* Tutt, 1906. *Nat. Hist. Brit. Butts.* 1(8/9): [261](#).
TS: *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834] by original designation ; *nec* Edwards & Haime, 1850. Brit. Foss. Corals (Pal. Soc. 3): lxvi.

Erynnis (Hesperopegasmus) marloyi (Boisduval, [1834])

[ORIG] *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834]. Icon. Hist. Lépid. 1: [241](#), [pl. 47](#), [fig. 6-7](#).

TL: Peloponnese (S Greece).

[JS] *Hesperia sericea* Freyer, [1839]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 3(45): [102](#), [pl. 265](#), [fig. 4](#).

TL: Constantinople (Turkey).

Tribe

Pyrgini Burmeister, 1878

[ORIG] Pyrgidae Burmeister, 1878. Descr. phys. Rép. Argentine 5: [245-246](#).

TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Pyrgus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [109](#).

TS: *Papilio alveolus* Hübner, 1800 (= *P. malvae* Linnaeus, 1758) by designation by Westwood, 1841. Brit. Butterflies Transf.: [120](#).

[JS] *Urbanus* Hübner, [1806]. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Syrichtus* Boisduval, [1834]. Icon. Hist. Lépid. 1: 230-232.

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1845. Hist. Nat. Ins. 2: [347-348](#).

Subgenus

Pyrgus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [109](#).

TS: *Papilio alveolus* Hübner, 1800 (= *P. malvae* Linnaeus, 1758) by designation by Westwood, 1841. Brit. Butterflies Transf.: [120](#).

[JS] *Urbanus* Hübner, [1806]. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha)* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 19, 72.

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) malvoides (Elwes & Edwards, 1897)

[ORIG] *Hesperia malvoides* Elwes & Edwards, 1897. Trans. Zool. Soc. Lond. 14(4): [156](#), [160](#), [pl. 23](#), [fig. 27-27a](#).

TL: Biarritz (SW France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race [ab.?] *australis* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [224](#).

TL: Draguignan (S France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225](#).

TL: Vernet-les-Bains (S France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *andalusica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225-226](#).

TL: Canales de la Sierra (Spain).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *alpina* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [226](#).

TL: Cogne (Aosta, NW Italy) ; *nec* Erschoff, 1874. Fedsch. Lepid. Turkestan : 24.

- [JS] *Syrichthus malvae* f. *fritillans* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Léop. comp. 4: [393-394](#), [679](#), [pl. 54, fig. 461-463](#).
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia malvoides* race *tutti* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: Locarno (Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha) malvoides* race *modestior* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [6-7](#).
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha) malvoides* f. *melotiformis* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [6-7](#).
TL: TL: Pian di Mugnone, Florence (Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus malvoides* race? *alpestris* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 42.
Replacement name, nom. nov. for *Hesperia malvae alpina* Tutt, 1906 nec Erschoff, 1874.

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) malvae (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
TL: Trosa (Sweden).
- [JS] *Papilio malvae minor* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [pl. 36, fig. 5](#), [1779]: [345-346](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Papilio sao* Bergsträsser, 1779. Nom. Ins. 2: [67](#), pl. 40, fig. 8-9.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio taras* Bergsträsser, 1780. Nom. Ins. 4: [40](#), [pl. 91, fig. 5-6](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [149](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio fritillum* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [91](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JH] *Papilio lavaterae* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [91](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, [1783].
- [JH] *Papilio fritillum* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 464-465](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio fritillum* Fabricius, 1787.
- [JS] *Papilio aveolus* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 466-467](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] [*Papilio*] *malvarum* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [198](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Hesperia cardui* Godart, [1824]. Encycl. Méth. Entomol. 9(2): [784-785](#).
TL: N Germany ; Lappland.
- [JS] *Syrichthus (Hesperia) malvae* race *elegantior* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [6](#).
TL: Rhone Valley (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus malvae* ssp. *luciaris* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [345-346](#).
TL: Lopperberg (C Switzerland).

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) melotis (Duponchel, [1834])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia melotis* Duponchel, [1834]. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [257-258](#), [pl. 42](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Isle of Milos, Greece (see Notes (1): error ?).
- [JS] *Hesperia hypoleucos* Lederer, 1855. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 5: [193](#), [pl. 1](#), [fig. 8](#).
TL: Lebanon.
- [JS] *Syrichthus malvae* f. *graecus* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [394](#), [679](#), [pl. 54](#), [fig. 468-469](#).
TL: Greece (see Notes (2): error ?).
- [JS] *Scelotrix melotis* ssp. *jordana* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [290](#), [pl. 15](#), [fig. 24-25](#), [pl. 16](#), [fig. 51-52](#).
TL: El Hammie (Jordan), Safed (Israël).
- [JS] *Hesperia pontica* Reverdin, 1914. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3(1): [66-72](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 6, 12](#), [pl. 4](#), [fig. 2-3](#).
TL: Amasya (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia melotis* ssp. *caucasica* Rjabov, 1926. Bull. Sci. Inst. Explor. Reg. Caucase Nord 1: [298](#).
TL: Dzheyrakh (Rep. Ingushetia, Russian Federation).

Subgenus

Scelotrix Rambur, 1858

- [ORIG] *Scelotrix* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [63-65](#).
TS: *Papilio carthami* Hübner, 1813 by designation by Watson, 1893. Proc. Zool. Soc. Lond. 1893: [64](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia* (*Teleomorpha*) Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 18, 72.
TS: *Papilio carthami* Hübner, [1813] by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) carthami (Hübner, [1813])

- [ORIG] *Papilio carthami* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 143](#), [fig. 720-723](#).
TL: S Germany.
- [ND] *Papilio fritillarius* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Austria ; nomen dubium (see de Jong, 1987. Zool. Meded. 61(26) : [371-385](#)).
- [RJ] *Papilio maluae* [sic] *maior* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [91](#).
TL: S Russian Federation ; rejected name by Opinion 1599 (ICZN, 1990: [160](#)).
- [JS] *Hesperia moeschleri* Herrich-Schäffer, [1854]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [175](#), [pl. \(Hesperides\) 7](#), [fig. 37-38](#).
TL: Sarepta (= Volgograd, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Scelotrix galactites* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [68](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Scelotrix* [sic] *carthami* var. *valesiaca* Mabille, 1875. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 5(Bull.): [ccxiv](#).
TL: Switzerland.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* var. *major* Mabille, 1904. Gen. Ins. 17: [82](#).
TL: Valais (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* var. *rühli* Mabille, 1904. Gen. Ins. 17: [82](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Syrichthus carthami* var. *nevadensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. lépid. comp. 4: [383-384](#), [pl. 55](#), [fig. 474](#).
TL: Lanjaron, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).

- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* race *speciosa* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [172-173](#).
TL: Isarco Valley (= Eisacktal, prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy)
- [JH] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *pyrenaica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [69, pl. 23, fig. 9-10](#).
TL: Gavarnie (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, France) ; nec *Hesperia malvae pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* f. *albana* Heinrich, 1928. Dt. Entomol. Z. 1928(3): [187](#).
TL: NW Spain.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* race *lucasi* Reverdin, 1929. Bull. Soc. lép. Genève 6(2): [91-92, pl. 2, fig. 5-6](#).
TL: Forêt de Benon (dep. Charente inférieure, France).
- [NN] *Hesperia carthami* race *microcarthami* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 8: 140.
Replacement name, nom. nov. for *Hesperia carthami pyrenaica* Warren, 1926 ; nec *Hesperia malvae pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *septentrionalis* Alberti, 1938. Stett. Entomol. Ztg. 99(2): [236-238](#).
TL: Bärwalde, Neumark (Germany).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *analoga* Alberti, 1938. Stett. Entomol. Ztg. 99(2): [244](#).
TL: Trebević, Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Pyrgus fritillarius* race *nemausensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 28-29.
TL: Champ de tir de Nîmes (dep. Gard, S France).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) sidae (Esper, [1784])

- [ORIG] *Papilio sidae* Esper, [1784]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [178-179, pl. 90 \(cont. 40\), fig. 3](#).
TL: Volga region (Russian Federation).
- [JH] *Hesperia onopordi* Herrich-Schäffer, [1848]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. \(Hesperides\) 6, fig. 31-32](#).
TL: -. ; nec *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 13, p.](#)
- [JH] *Hesperia sidae* race *occidentalis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: W Europe ; nec *Hesperia serratulae occidentalis* Lucas, 1910. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1910: [62](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia sidae* race *occidua* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [76](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus sidae* ssp. *gargantoi* Martínez & Sánchez, 1987. Shilap 15(60): 371-375.
TL: Hervás (prov. Cáceres, Extremadura, Spain).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) centaureae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia centaureae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 10](#), [1840]: 315-316 (nota).
TL: Tornio and Dalarna (Sweden) or Abisko in Torne Lappmark (N Sweden) (see Opheim, 1959. Astarte 18: [2](#)).
- [JS] *Pyrgus centaureae* ssp. *schöyeni* Opheim, 1959. Astarte 18: [4, fig. 1](#).
TL: Odalen (S Norway).
- [JS] *Pyrgus centaureae lineolata* Kauffmann, 1950. Entomol. Z. 59(23): [177-180, fig.](#)
TL: 'Halbinsel Rybatschi an der Murmanküste' (?? Russian Federation).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) cacaliae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cacaliae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 6-7, k](#), [1840]: 313-314 (nota).
TL: Alps (SE France).

- [JS] *Hesperia cacaliae cantoniera* Belling, 1926. Int. Entomol. Z. 20: 198.
TL: St. Gotthardo, Ticino Alps (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cacaliae* race *prosensis* Kauffmann, 1946. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 41: [75-81, fig. 1-3](#).
TL: St. Gotthardo, Ticino Alps (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus (Scelotrix) cacaliae* race *pyrenaicus* Picard, 1947. Rev. fr. Lépid. 11(4): 94-95.
TL: Masivul Bucegi, above Sinaia, jud. Prahova (Romania).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cacaliae* ssp. *hebsgaardii* Bjerregård & Mølgaard, 2023. Phegea 51(1): [42-46, fig.](#)
TL: Masivul Bucegi, above Sinaia, jud. Prahova (Romania).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) andromedae (Wallengren, 1853)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus andromedae* Wallengren, 1853. Öfversigt Kongl. Vetenskaps-akad. förhandl. 10(2): [25](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JS] *Syrichthus andromedae* var. *borealis* Stichel, 1908. Berl. Entomol. Z. 20: [198](#).
TL: Tysfjorden (N Norway).

Subgenus

Ateleomorpha Warren, 1926

- [ORIG] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha)* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 19, 87.
TS: *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839] by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) serratulae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia serratulae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. And. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 9, m](#), [1840]: 318-319.
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Hesperia caecus* Freyer, [1847]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(83): [22, pl. 493, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Tyrol (Austria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus serratulae* var. *major* Staudinger, 1878. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 14: [292](#).
TL: Kerasdere, Taurus (Turkey).
- [JH] *Syrichthus serratulae minor* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Emtomol. Comp. 4: [401, 680, pl. 55, fig. 482](#).
TL: Cauterets (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, France) ; nec *Papilio malvae minor* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(1): [pl. 36, fig. 5](#).
- [JH] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *occidentalis* Lucas, 1910. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1910: [62](#).
TL: Fontenay-le-Comte (dep. Vendée, W France) ; nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906. Entomol. News 17(3): [96](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *planorum* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Friedland (Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, NE Germany).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *fragilis* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria).
- [JH] *Hesperia serratulae* f. *latealbata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Schynige Platte (Bern, C Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* ssp. *balcanica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): 97-98, pl. 29, fig. 7-12.
TL: Cetinje (Montenegro).

- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* ssp. *uralensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): 98-99, pl. 29, fig. 1-6.
TL: Uralsk (Kazakhstan).
- [NN] *Hesperia serratulae magnagallica* Verity, 1931. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 36(13): [201](#).
Replacement name for *Hesperia serratulae* var. *occidentalis* Lucas, 1910 nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906.
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *clarissima* Heinrich, 1938. Dt. Entomol. Z. 'Iris' 52: 15, fig.
TL: Digne (SE France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus serratulae* race *infraobscurata* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var 50(suppl.): [3](#).
TL: Skala, S. Dionisio (Greece).
- [JS] *Pyrgus serratulae* race *arvernensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 35.
TL: France.
- [JS] *Hesperia (Pyrgus) serratulae* ssp. *grisescens* Alberti, 1969. Faun. Abhandl. Staatl. Mus. Tierk. Dresden 2(20): [141-142, fig. 3](#).
TL: Teberda (Karachay-Cherkessia, Russian Federation).

***Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) armoricanus* (Oberthür, 1910)**

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *armoricanus* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [411-413](#), [681](#), pl. 57, fig. 509-517.
TL: Rennes (C France).
- [JS] *Hesperia persica* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 2(4): 218-224, pl. 21, fig. 4, pl. 22, fig. 9.
TL: Kuldsar (Iran).
- [IFS] *Hesperia armoricanus* gen.II *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: -.
- [JH] *Syrichthus armoricanus* var. *corsicus* Oberthür, 1919. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1919(7): [130](#).
TL: Corsica (S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus* race *rufosatura* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [73](#).
TL: Fontebuona di Vaglia (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus petheri* Romei, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(9): [127](#).
TL: Cuenca (C Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia persica* var. *prostanae* Pfeiffer, 1927. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 17: [45-46](#).
TL: inner Anatolia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) armoricanus* f. *cacaotica* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [15](#).
TL: Valle umida del Camaione (prov. Lucca, Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus philonides* Hemming, 1931. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (10)8: 534-535.
TL: Khan Ghaffa (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus* ssp. *disjuncta* Alberti, 1940. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 30(1): [252-253](#), pl. 2, fig. 7a.
TL: Halle (Germany).
- [SN] *Pyrgus armoricanus* race *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 70, pl. 3, fig. 14-31.
TL: Valle del Camaione (Lucca), Monte Conca (Firenze) (Italy) ; Stat. nov. for *Hesperia armoricanus* gen.II *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1919.
- [JS] *Pyrgus armoricanus maroccanus* Picard, 1950. Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Maroc 28: [121-122](#).
TL: Ifrane (Maroc).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) alveus (Hübner, [1803])

- [ORIG] *Papilio alveus* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 461-463](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Pyrgus alveus-fritillum* var. *funginus* Schilde, 1886. Berl. Entomol. Z. 30: [39-49](#).
TL: Vintschgau (prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* var. *scandinavicus* Strand, 1903. Arch. Math. Naturvid. 25: [6-8](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JH] *Syrichthus alveus* race *ryffelensis* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [405-408](#), [679](#), [pl. 54, fig. 470-471](#).
TL: Zermatt, Ryffelalp (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Syrichthus alveus* race *ballotae* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404](#), [680](#), [pl. 56, fig. 494-495](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* var. *alticola* Rebel, 1910. In: Berge's, Schmetterlingsbuch (ed. 9): [84](#).
TL: Stilsferjoch, Stelvio Pass (N Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *centralitaliae* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: Piceno, Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *accreta* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [55](#).
TL: Simplon, ... (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *grandis* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [55](#).
TL: Saint-Martin-Vésubie (dep. Alpes-Maritimes, SE France).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* f. *centralhispaniae* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [56](#).
TL: Albarracin (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia ryffelensis* race *albans* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [56](#).
TL: Olmütz, Moravia (=Olomouc, Czech Republic).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *trebevicensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [121](#).
TL: Trebević (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *jurassica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [121-122](#), [pl. 42, fig. 9-12](#).
TL: Grand Salève (Jura, E France).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *pyrenealpium* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [11](#).
TL: Gèdre (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *necaccreta* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [12](#).
TL: Vall de Núria (prov. Girona, NE Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *magnalveus* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [12](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *insigniamiscens* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [13-14](#).
TL: Font Quer, Horeajo, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JH] *Syrichthus alveus* race *claralveus* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [10-11](#).
TL: Cesana (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JH] *Hesperia alveus* f. *caucasius* Picard, 1949. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 12: 57.
TL: Monts Adjara, Kuban (South Caucasus).

- [JS] *Pyrgus alveus* ssp. *prabornius* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [357-358](#).
TS: Saas Fee, Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus reverdini* ssp. *scotti* Warren, 1952. Entomologist 85: 39-41.
TL: Sylkynjärvi, Savonlinna (Finland).
- [JH] *Pyrgus* (*A.*) *illensis* ssp. *colurnus* Kauffmann, 1954. Redia 39: 261-274, pl. 2, fig.
TL: Rhaetian Alps, Piedmont, Alto Adige, Lombardy (N Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus trebevicensis* ssp. *germanica* Renner, 1983. Caroleinea 41: [133](#).
TL: Schwäbische Alb, Schmiechtal, Hütten (S Germany).
- [ND] *Pyrgus alveus* ssp. *confusa* Renner, 1983. Caroleinea 41: [133-134](#).
TL: ? Alpes ; Nomen nudum.

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) warrenensis (Verity, 1928)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia alveus* race *warrenensis* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1928(8): [140-141](#).
TL: Lenzerheide (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JH] *Pyrgus warrenensis* ssp. *occidentalis* Renner, 1991. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 28: [94, pl. 8, fig. 36, pl. 27, fig. 190-193](#).
TL: Grossglockner (Carinthia, Austria) ; nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906. Entomol. News 17(3): [96](#).
- [JS] *Pyrgus warrenensis dejongensis* Taymans C., 1992. Bull. Cercle Lépid. Belg./Bull. Belg. Lepid. Kring 21(6): [126-127](#).
TL: Larche (Basses-Alpes, SE France).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) bellieri (Oberthür, 1910)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* var. *bellieri* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-406, 680, pl. 56, fig. 490-491](#).
TL: Larche (dep. Alpes-de-Haute-Provence, SE France).
- [JH] *Hesperia carthami* Duponchel, 1832. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [pl. 42, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Provence (S France) ; nec Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 143, fig. 720-723](#).
- [JH] *Hesperia alveus* Duponchel, 1832. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [259-260](#).
TL: Provence (S France) ; nec Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 461-463](#).
- [JS] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *foulquieri* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-406, 680, pl. 56, fig. 487-489](#).
TL: Saint Zacharie (dep. Var, SE France).
- [JS] *Hesperia foulquieri* race *picena* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia foulquieri* f. *supra-bellieri* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: S. France.
- [JS] *Hesperia bellieri* race *nigropicta* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7-8): [103](#).
TL: Oulx, Cesana, Clavières. (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* var. *gaillardi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 37.
TL: dep. Gard (S France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* ssp. *adkini* Picard, 1948. Rev. fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 327.
TL: Bagnols-les-Bains (dep. Lozère, S France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* ssp. *corsicae* Renner, 1991. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 28: [66, pl. 1, fig. 4, pl. 9, fig. 47-48](#).
TL: Evisa (Corsica, S France).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) numida (Oberthür, 1910)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *numida* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-405](#), [680](#), [pl. 55, fig. 484-486](#).
TL: Tazoult (NE Algeria).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) onopordi (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 13, p.](#) [1840]: 319-320.
TL: Granada (Andalusia, S Spain).
[JS] *Pyrgus conyzae* Guenée, 1877. Petites Nouv. Entomol. (2)9(175): [145](#).
TL: Voirons, Savoie (E France).
[JS] *Syrichthus onopordi quercii* Oberthür, 1912. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 6: [107](#), [345](#), [pl. 143, fig. 1328-1330](#).
TL: Polleca (Monti Aurunci, C Italy).
[IFS] *Hesperia onopordi* gen.II. *fulvotincta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Firenze (Toscany, Italy).
[JS] *Hesperia onopordi* race *pallidissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [73-74](#).
TL: Sierra de Albarracin (Aragon, C. Spain).
[SN] *Hesperia onopordi* race *fulvotincta* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [74](#).
Stat. nov. for *Hesperia onopordi* gen.II. *fulvotincta* Verity, 1919.

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) carlinae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia carlinae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 11, n.](#) [1840]: 314-315 (nota).
TL: Alps (France ; Switzerland).
[JS] *Syrichthus carlinae* f. *olivacea* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [409](#), [680](#), [pl. 56, fig. 497-498](#).
TL: La Graves (dep. Hautes-Alpes, France).
[JS] *Hesperia carlinae* race *atrata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [57](#).
TL: Formazza Valley (Piedmont, NW Italy).
[JS] *Pyrgus carlinae* ssp. *ochroides* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [352](#).
TL: Val Bedretto (Ticino, Switzerland).
[JS] *Pyrgus carlinae* race *cottiana* Kauffmann, 1955. Boll. Soc. Entomol. It. 84: [139-140, fig. 2](#).
TL: Cottian Alps (NW Italy).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) cirsii (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cirsii* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 12, o.](#) [1840]: 315 (nota).
TL: Fontainebleau (C. France).
[auct] *Papilio fritillum* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [159](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria).
[JS] *Scelothrix cynarae* var. *iberica* Grum-Grshimailo, 1893. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 27(3-4): [384-385](#).
TL: Spain.
[JS] *Syrichthus cirsii* var. *herrichii* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [410](#), [681](#), [pl. 56, fig. 508](#).
TL: Sierra Alta (prov. Teruel, Spain).

- [JS] *Syrichtus armoricanus* var. *fabressei* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [412](#), [681](#), [pl. 57, fig. 518-520](#).
TL: Sierra Alta (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia fritillum* f. *parafabressei* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [72](#).
TL: Digne (SE France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus fritillum* ssp. *turcivola* Lattin, 1950. Istanb. Univ. Fen Fak. Mecm. (B)15(4): 326, pl. 2, fig. 6.
TL: Nemrut Dagi (prov. Bitlis, E Turkey).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cirsii* ssp. *tramelanensis* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [354-355](#).
TL: Schweizer Jura (Switzerland).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) cinarae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cinarae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 4-5, j](#).
TL: Sarepta (Volga reg., Russian Federation).
- [JH] *Hesperia cynarae* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [36](#).
TL: Taganrok (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Hesperia cinarae* ssp. *clorinda* Warren, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(6): [81-82](#).
TL: Tragacete (prov. Cuenca, C Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia cinarae* f. *atrata* Thurner, 1938. Mitt. Naturwiss. Inst. Sofia 11: [137, fig.](#)
TL: Petrino (S North Macedonia).

Conclusion

This synonymic list offers a foundation for the taxonomy of Western Palearctic Hesperidae.

By linking each name to its original description, it enhances transparency, accessibility, and historical accuracy. However, the list is not yet complete, and gaps remain in both hyperlinks and taxonomic data. Researchers, lepidopterists and enthusiasts are warmly invited to contribute by submitting missing hyperlinks, overlooked synonyms, or other relevant information.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

Additional notes on the fauna of Mount Žeden (North Macedonia) in late spring 2025 (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea & Zygaenidae)

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Abstract

A first visit to Mount Žeden in April 2025 (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025) enabled the observation of several species of interest for the Papilionoidea fauna of North Macedonia, including *Proterebia phegea* (Borkhausen, 1788), a species newly for the country. A second visit was scheduled for mid-June of the same year to refine our knowledge and confirmed the importance of this region for the conservation of the Lepidoptera fauna of North Macedonia.

Key words

Papilionoidea — faunistics — conservation — Mount Žeden — North Macedonia — Balkan Peninsula.

Introduction

The observations made at the beginning of spring 2025 on Mt. Žeden demonstrated the richness of its Lepidoptera fauna (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025). To further our knowledge and obtain additional insights into this fauna, the site was revisited at the end of spring on 13.vi.2025.

The rather dry climate in this region (fewer than fifteen days of light rain between April 15th and June 13th) combined with the high temperatures (with maxima exceeding 25°C during the same period) had markedly altered the landscape compared with the first visit. The vegetation was extremely dry, and butterflies were scarce in the lower part of the mountain. Seasonal development was clearly advanced, with several species recorded that normally fly later in the year. On the day of the biotope survey, the temperature in the shade exceeded 30°C.

Biotopes and observations

Only the southern part of Mt. Žeden, situated north of the village of Boyanë, was explored on 13.vi.2025. A total of 47 species of Papilionoidea and six species of Zygaenidae were recorded at different elevations of the mountain.

A. The lower grassland zone at approximately 400–500 m a.s.l. was very dry, and butterflies were scarce. Only the following species were recorded:

Iphiclides podalirius (Linnaeus, 1758), *Papilio machaon* Linnaeus, 1758, *Leptidea sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Colias croceus* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Polyommatus icarus* (Rottemburg, 1775), *Issoria lathonia* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Coenonympha pamphilus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

All these species had already been recorded previously in April 2025, though some were likely from a subsequent generation.

B. The mid-elevation valley (Fig. 1a-c), at approximately 500–900 m a.s.l., was relatively unaffected by the drought, and the vegetation remained green and in bloom. Butterflies were abundant in both species and numbers:

I. podalirius, *P. machaon*, *Ochlodes sylvanus* (Esper, 1777), *Thymelicus lineola* (Ochsenheimer, 1808), *Spialia orbifer* (Hübner, [1823]), *Spialia phlomidis* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845]), *Pyrgus malvae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pyrgus carthami* (Hübner, [1813]), *Pyrgus armoricanus* (Oberthür, 1910), *L. sinapis*, *Leptidea duponcheli* (Staudinger, 1871), *Gonepteryx rhamni* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Colias alfacariensis* Ribbe, 1905, *C. croceus*, *Aporia crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pontia edusa* (Fabricius, 1777), *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pieris manni* (Mayer, 1851), *Pieris ergane* (Geyer, [1828]), *Pieris balcana* Lorković, [1969], *Lycaena phlaeas* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Satyrrium ilicis* (Esper, [1779]), *Satyrrium spini* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Tarucus balkanica* (Freyer, [1843]), *Cupido minimus* (Fuessly, 1775), *Plebejus idas* (Linnaeus, 1761), *Aricia anteros* (Freyer, 1839), *Lysandra bellargus* (Rottemburg, 1775), *P. icarus*, *Polyommatus thersites* (Cantener, 1835), *Limenitis camilla* (Linnaeus, 1764), *I. lathonia*, *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Vanessa atalanta* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Nymphalis polychloros* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Melitaea didyma* (Esper, [1778]), *Melitaea cinxia* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Melitaea athalia* (Rottemburg, 1775), *C. pamphilus*, *Maniola jurtina* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Melanargia larissa* (Geyer, [1828]), *Melanargia galathea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hipparchia volgensis* (Mazochin-Porshnjakov, 1952) (male genitalia verified) and *Chazara briseis* (Linnaeus, 1764). Zygaenidae were represented by the following species: *Zygaena carniolica* (Scopoli, 1763), *Zygaena loti* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *Zygaena angelicae* Ochsenheimer, 1808 and *Zygaena filipendulae* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Notably, *S. phlomidis* had already been observed on April 19th. While a single generation with widely spaced emergences is a plausible hypothesis, the possibility of two successive generations cannot be excluded. Continuous monitoring of this species throughout the year would be required to confirm its phenology.

Fig. 1a-b. Two examples illustrating the richness of the fauna and flora in this mid-elevation valley: *Syntomis marjana* Stauder, 1913 (Lepidoptera: Arctiinae) and martagon lily, *Lilium martagon* (Liliopsida: Liliaceae) (Photo: Bénédicte Jonckers).

Fig. 1c. Mid-elevation valley at approximately 800 m a.s.l., habitat of *Spialia phlomidis*. (Photo: Bénédicte Jonckers)

C. The summit zone, at approximately 900–1.200 m a.s.l. was relatively poor in butterfly numbers. *Proterebia phegea*, which had been abundant in this area in April, was no longer present. Most of the butterflies observed were badly damaged, suggesting that the populations of these species had not been renewed by recent emergences. However, some species present at this altitude had not been observed at lower altitudes. These are marked with (*) in the following list:

Favria cribrillum (Eversmann, 1841) (*), *C. croceus*, *A. crataegi*, *P. rapae*, *P. icarus*, *Polyommatus amandus* (Schneider, 1792) (*), *I. lathonia*, *Brenthis hecate* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (*), *V. atalanta*, *N. polychloros*, *C. pamphilus*, *M. jurtina*, *M. galathea* and *H. volgensis* (male genitalia verified). Zygaenidae were represented by the following species: *Zygaena purpuralis* (Brünnich, 1763) (*), *Z. angelicae* and *Zygaena loniceræ* (Scheven, 1777) (*).

The most interesting observation is certainly *F. cribrillum*. Only a single female specimen was seen, which was already quite worn.

However, some uncertainty remains regarding the identification of the specimen, particularly in relation to *Muschampia tessellum* (Hübner, [1803]). The following criteria (Fig. 3) support assignment to *F. cribrillum*:

- a) The four white spots are irregular; the longest are rectangular (in contrast, *M. tessellum* usually has only three less-angular spots).
 - b) The discoidal spot is straight proximally and forms an angle distally (in *M. tessellum*, this spot is more rounded and the proximal edge less straight).
- The geographical distribution of this species in Europe is highly fragmented. It has been recorded in Greece (Davkov & Mérit 2017, 2018), Bulgaria (Kolev 2003; Hoejgaard & Beshkov 2011; Langourov 2019; Wagner & Kolev 2019), Serbia (Popović Đurić Franeta & Verovnik 2013; Popović & Đurić 2014; Langourov 2019; Vujić, Đurić & Tot 2020), Romania (see references compiled in Dincă Kolev & Verovnik 2010), Russia (Eversmann 1841), and Ukraine (Nekrutenko & Tshikolovets 2005). In North Macedonia, the species is known from fewer than ten localities (see inventory below). Its presence in Hungary remains uncertain. For North Macedonia, the following sites are cited in the literature, listed in the chronological order of their publication:
- a) The eastern slopes of Mount Suva Planina near the village of Nova Breznica, 17 km southwest of Skopje (Lorković 1983);
 - b) Two mapped data points taken from a UTM grid, 34T EM 21 and 34T EM 24 (Schaidler & Jakšić 1989), the first of which has not been subsequently confirmed;
 - c) The southern slopes of Mount Vodno (Verovnik & Micevski 2009);
 - d) Grupčin village (Dincă, Kolev & Verovnik 2010), based on a personal communication from P. Russel;
 - e) Regarding the distribution of the species in North Macedonia, Dincă *et al.* (2010) conclude: "In the Republic of Macedonia, judging from the precisely known records and satellite imagery, the potential area where *M. cribrillum* may occur extends in an arc from Raduša village near the border with Kosovo and Mount Vodno just westward south of Skopje to Gostivar town and then south to Brod and Debrešte villages. Further research in this lepidopterologically very rich region, including a verification of the record from the vicinity of Gorna Belica in Schaidler & Jakšić (1989), is desirable."
 - f) Mt. Zheden (Davkov & Mérit 2017) without further details on the locality; is this a reference to the locality of Grupčin (point d. above) which is located at the foot of Mt. Zheden?
- The closest known populations in Europe are, to the south, on Mount Olympus (Greece) and to the northeast, in the Stara Planina Mountains of Serbia and Bulgaria. These lie approximately 220 km and 180 km respectively from the biotopes of North Macedonia.

F. cribrellum is included in the European Red List of Butterflies (van Swaay *et al.* 2025) with the status VU (Vulnerable) and the criteria B2ab(iii,v). These criteria indicate a very small area of occupancy, a highly fragmented population or a limited number of localities, and an observed, inferred or predicted continued decline in habitat quality and in the number of mature individuals.

Fig. 2. *F. cribrellum* ♀, Mt Žeden, 1000 m a.s.l., (42.020138° N, 21.177992° E), 13.vi.2025. Leg. Michel Taymans.

Fig. 3. Distribution of *F. cribrellum* in North Macedonia. (Map: Michel Taymans)

- Localities cited in the literature;
- The observation location on Mt. Žeden;
- The uncertain locality cited by Schaidler & Jakšić (1989), UTM grid: 34T EM 21.

Conclusions

Overall, across the four visits conducted in early and late spring 2025 (19.iv.2025, 20.iv.2025, 30.iv.2025 and 13.vi.2025), a total of 64 species of Papilionoidea and 6 species of Zygaenidae were recorded. The occurrence of *Proterebia phegea*, for which, as far as is known, Mount Žeden is the only habitat in North Macedonia, the presence of *F. cribrellum*, a species regarded as Vulnerable at the European level, together with numerous species listed on the Red List of North Macedonia (Krpac & Darcemont 2022) and several other Balkan endemics, confirms that Mount Žeden represents an emblematic site for the Lepidoptera fauna of North Macedonia.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualization, field work, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Bénédicte Jonckers: field work, writing – review and editing.

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References

Davkov S. & Mérit X. 2017. *Muschampia cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1841) new to the Greek butterfly fauna and found in an unexpected alpine ecosystem (Lepidoptera: Hesperidae). — *Lépidoptères, Revue des Lépidoptéristes de France* 26(66): 38–42.

- Davkov S. & Mérit X. 2018. *Muschampia cribrellum inexpectata*, a new subspecies from Mt Olympus, Greece (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae). — *Lépidoptères, Revue de Lépidoptéristes de France* 27(69): 2–11. ([url](#))
- Dincă V., Kolev Z. & Verovnik R. 2010. The distribution, ecology and conservation status of the Spinose Skipper *Muschampia cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1841) at the western limit of its range in Europe (HesperIIDae). — *Nota Lepidopterologica* 33(1): 39–57. ([url](#))
- Eversmann E. 1841. Nachricht ueber einige noch unbeschriebene Schmetterlinge des oestlichen Russlands. — *Bulletin de la Société impériale des naturalistes de Moscou* 1841(1): 18-27, pl. 3. ([url](#)).
- Franeta F. & Gascoigne-Pees M. 2022. The lifecycle and ecology of the Spinose Skipper - *Favria cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1841) in the Republic of North Macedonia (Lepidoptera, HesperIIDae). — *Nota Lepidopterologica* 45: 119-127. ([url](#))
- Hoejgaard K. & Beshkov S. 2011. Rediscovering *Muschampia tessellum* ([Hübner, [1803]]) in Bulgaria with additional notes on *M. cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1814) from the Eastern Balkan (Stara Planina) mountains. — *Entomologist's Record and Journal of Variation* 123: 147–150. ([url](#))
- Kolev Z. 2003. First record of *Muschampia cribrellum* in Bulgaria, with a review of the recorded distribution of genus *Muschampia* in the country (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae). — *Phegea* 31(1): 15–21. ([url](#))
- Krpač V. & Darceumont C. 2012. Red list of butterflies (Lepidoptera: Hesperioidea & Papilionoidea) for Republic of Macedonia. — *Revue Ecologie (Terre Vie)* 67: 117–122. ([url](#))
- Langourov M. 2019. New data on the butterflies of Western Stara Planina Mts (Bulgaria & Serbia) (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). — *Ecologica Montenegrina* 20: 119–162. ([url](#))
- Lorković Z. 1983. A new *Syrichtus* and two doubtful *Pyrgus* species for the fauna of Yugoslavia (Lep., HesperIIDae). — *Acta entomologica Jugoslavica* 19: 33-41. ([url](#))
- Nekrutenko Y. & Tshikolovets V. 2005. *The Butterflies of Ukraine*. — Kyiv: Rayevsky Scientific Publishers (Ed.). 231 p.
- Popović M., Đurić M., Franeta F. & Verovnik R. 2013. On the extremely rich butterfly fauna (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera) of the south-eastern foothills of Stara Planina Mts in Serbia. — *Phegea* 41(4): 74-81 ([url](#)), annex 1-7. ([url](#))
- Popović M. & Đurić M. 2014. *Dnevni leptiri Stare planine. Butterflies of Stara Planina*. — Beograd: Srbijašume and HabiProt (Ed.). 208 p.
- Schaider P. & Jakšić P. N. 1989. *Die Tagfalter von jugoslawisch Mazedonien*. — Ljubljana: Druckerei. J. Pleško (Ed.). 199 p.
- Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. 2025. Exploration of Mount Žeden and discovery of *Proterebia phegea* (Borkhausen, 1788), a new species for the fauna of North Macedonia. — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(2): 21-30. ([url](#))
- Verovnik R. & Micevski B. 2009. On the presence of *Syrichtus cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1841) (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae) in the Republic of Macedonia. — *Entomologist's Gazette* 60: 232–236. ([url](#))
- van Swaay C., Warren M., Ellis S., Clay J., Bellotto V., Allen D.J. & Trottet A. 2025. *Measuring the pulse of European biodiversity. European Red List of Butterflies*. — Brussels, Belgium: European Commission (Ed.). x-80 p. ([url](#))
- Vujić M., Đurić M. & Tot I. 2020. New localities for rare butterflies *Muschampia cribrellum* and *Melitaea ornata* (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae, Nymphalidae) in Serbia. — *Acta Entomologica Slovenica* 28(2): 159-164. ([url](#))
- Wagner W. & Kolev Z. 2019. *Muschampia cribrellum* (Eversmann, 1841) – preimaginal stages and their ecology in W-Bulgaria (Lepidoptera: HesperIIDae). — *Nachrichten des Entomologischen Vereins Apollo*, N. F. 40(2): 113–117. ([url](#))

**Toward a revised checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies, hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)
Part III: Rationale and framework for the Pieridae.**

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Abstract

Taxonomic and nomenclatural issues concerning the butterfly family Pieridae are reviewed in light of the rules of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), historical classifications, recent phylogenetic studies and current usage. Particular attention is given to the classification of subfamilies and tribes, where older names and synonymies have sometimes conflicted with prevailing usage, requiring rigorous evaluation under the Code.

At the tribal level, the status of Aporiini is discussed. The various interpretations concerning the species composition of certain genera are examined, and the decisions adopted for the compilation of the checklist are explained, particularly for the genera *Leptidea*, *Gonepteryx* and *Colias*. The status of the genus *Belenois* and its placement within the classification, including the resulting modifications to the checklist, are clarified. Finally, the generic structure within the tribe Anthocharidini is analysed.

Key words

Taxonomy — Checklist — Papilionoidea — Pieridae — Dismorphiinae — Coliadinae — Pierinae — Aporiini — Anthocharidini — *Leptidea* — *Leptidea morsei* — *Gonepteryx* — *Colias* — *Belenois* — *Euchloe* — *Iberochloe* — *Elphinstonia* — *Anthocharis* — *Euchloe pechi* — *Zegris meridionalis* — Western Palearctic.

Introduction

Nomenclatural stability within Pieridae requires consistent application of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature combined with careful consideration of historical usage and current taxonomic practice. Despite extensive study, the family remains affected by long-standing issues arising from historical name proliferation, changing generic and subfamilial concepts, and differing regional interpretations. Recent molecular studies have clarified several relationships but have also produced conflicting or incomplete results, particularly where taxon sampling is limited. The present revised checklist of Western Palearctic Pieridae Nomenclatural stability within Pieridae requires consistent application of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature combined with careful consideration of historical usage and current taxonomic practice. Despite extensive study, the family remains affected by long-standing issues arising from historical name proliferation, changing generic and subfamilial concepts, and differing regional interpretations. Recent molecular studies have clarified several relationships but have also produced conflicting or incomplete results, particularly where taxon sampling is limited. The present revised checklist of West Palearctic Pieridae therefore follows a pragmatic approach, retaining well-established names where justified, applying ICZN provisions consistently, and documenting the rationale for each taxonomic decision. Unresolved cases are explicitly identified, providing a transparent and stable reference framework while indicating areas where further integrative research is required.

1. Classification of Tribes in the Subfamily Pierinae

1.1. Introduction

The group-family level classification adopted in the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), encompassing superfamilies, families, subfamilies, tribes and subtribes, largely follows the most recent phylogenetic studies on Pieridae (Braby *et al.* 2006; Wahlberg *et al.* 2014; Ding & Zhang 2016; Wei *et al.*, 2022; Kawahara *et al.*, 2023; Carvalho *et al.* 2024), with the notable exception of the Aporiini. The rationale for this exception and the approach adopted are discussed below.

1.2. Context

Unfortunately, the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN) provides no biological, morphological, phylogenetic or genetic criteria for the recognition of taxa at the group-family level. The Code regulates nomenclature rather than taxa themselves and therefore does not define what constitutes a family or how it should be delineated.

Prior to phylogenetic analyses, group-family ranks were assigned at the discretion of individual systematists, based on a variety of criteria. These could include the structure of the exoskeleton, wing venation, legs, palpi, genitalia or life-history traits such as eggs, larvae and pupae. By considering these characteristics, systematists aimed to provide a conceptual framework for grouping species progressively into increasingly smaller sets, ultimately resulting in genus-level classifications that comprised only a few species.

In contrast, contemporary phylogenetic studies adopt a more objective approach by linking taxonomic ranks to the historical timing of lineage divergences. For instance, in Kawahara *et al.* (2023), the temporal intervals used to define classification levels are: families between 100 and 80 Ma, subfamilies between 80 and 60 Ma, tribes between 60 and 40 Ma, and subtribes between 40 and 20 Ma. This method is therefore anchored in estimated divergence times derived from mathematical models and can be considered less subjectively influenced. These intervals do not necessarily correspond to geological epochs (e.g., the 60 to 40 Ma interval used to define tribes spans the mid-Palaeocene to mid-Eocene). Nevertheless, the advantage of this approach is that it bases classification on a consistent, objective criterion, whereas its drawback is the exclusion of other potentially informative characteristics.

1.3. Conclusion

Regarding the Aporiini/Aporiina, Kawahara *et al.* (2023) recognise the group's monophyly but include it within the Pierini. Their supplementary phylogenetic tree indicates that the Aporiini/Aporiina branch diverged from the Pierini at an estimated 36 Ma. Thus, based on an estimated 4 Ma divergence interval (subjectively calculated), the Aporiini/Aporiina are treated as a subtribe.

The last author to consider Aporiini/Aporiina at the tribe level was Braby (2005) in his *Provisional Checklist of Genera of the Pieridae*. What is the rationale for following this relatively older study rather than more recent ones? First, from a technical perspective, available evidence strongly supports the monophyly of the group. Second, although it is represented by a single species in the European fauna, the group is widely distributed globally, encompassing over 400 species. Recognizing it as a tribe allows for further subdivision into subtribes; for example, *Belenois* (and closely related genera) could constitute a distinct subtribe, separate from *Delias* (and related genera) or other genus-level clusters.

1.4. References

Braby M. 2005. Provisional checklist of genera of the Pieridae (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). — *Zootaxa* 832: 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.832.1.1>

Braby M., Vila R. & Pierce N. 2006. Molecular phylogeny and systematics of the Pieridae (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea): higher classification and biogeography. — *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 147: 239–275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.2006.00218.x>

Carvalho A., Owens H., St Laurent R., Earl C., Dexter K., Messcher R., Willmott K., Aduse-Poku K., Collins C., Homziak N., Hoshizaki S., Hsu Y., Kizhakke A., Kunte K., Martins D., Mega N., Morinaka S., Peggie D., Romanowski H., Sáfián S., Vila R., Wang H., Braby M., Espeland M., Breinholt J., Pierce N., Kawahara A., Lohman D. 2024. Comprehensive phylogeny of Pieridae butterflies reveals strong correlation between diversification and temperature. — *iScience* 27(4): (109336): 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.109336>

Ding C. & Zhang Y. 2016. Phylogenetic relationships of Pieridae (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) in China based on seven gene fragments. — *Entomological Science* 20(1): 15-23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ens.12214>

Kawahara A., Storer C., Carvalho A., Plotkin D., Condamine F., Braga M., Ellis E., St Laurent R., Li X., Barve V., Cai L., Earl C., Frandsen B., Owens H., Valencia-Montoya W., Aduse-Poku K., Toussaint E., Dexter K., Doleck T., Markee A., Messcher R., Nguyen Y., Badon J., Benítez H., Braby M., Buenavente P., Chan W., Collins S., Rabideau Childers R., Dankowicz E., Eastwood R., Fric Z., Gott R., Hall J., Hallwachs W., Hardy N., Hawkins Sipe R., Heath A., Hinolan J., Homziak N., Hsu Y., Inayoshi Y., Iltiong M., Janzen D., Kitching I., Kunte K., Lamas G., Landis M., Larsen E., Larsen T., Leong J., Lukhtanov V., Maier C., Martinez J., Martins D., Maruyama K., Maunsell S., Mega N., Monastyrskii A., Morais A., Müller C., Naive M., Nielsen G., Padrón P., Peggie D., Romanowski H., Sáfián S., Saito M., Schröder S., Shirey V., Soltis D., Soltis P., Sourakov A., Talavera G., Vila R., Vlasanek P., Wang H., Warren A., Willmott K., Yago M., Jetz W., Jarzyna M., Breinholt J., Espeland M., Ries L., Guralnick R., Pierce N. & Lohman D. 2023. A global phylogeny of butterflies reveals their evolutionary history, ancestral hosts and biogeographic origins. — *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7: 903-913. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02041-9>. Supplementary Materials: [url](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02041-9).

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

Wahlberg N., Rota J., Braby M., Pierce N. & Wheat C. 2014. Revised systematics and higher classification of pierid butterflies (Lepidoptera: Pieridae) based on molecular data. — *Zoologica Scripta*, 43, 641–650. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zsc.12075>.

Wei F., Huang W., Fang L., He B., Zhao Y., Zhang Y., Shu Z., Su C. & Hao J. 2023. Spatio-Temporal Evolutionary Patterns of the Pieridae Butterflies (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) Inferred from Mitogenomic Data. — *Genes* 14(1):72. Article: <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes14010072>. Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

2. Classification within the Genus *Leptidea* Billberg, 1820

2.1. Reference classification

Since the discovery of a new species within the genus *Leptidea* by Real (1988), researchers (Lorković 1993; Mazel 2000–2002; ...) have examined this genus in detail, first using classical methods (such as genitalia) and later based on DNA or karyological data, which led to the discovery of a second new, cryptic species (Dincă *et al.* 2011).

Entomologists are therefore confronted with newly recognised species that cannot be reliably identified in the field by their habitus. *Leptidea reali* Reissinger, [1990] and *Leptidea juvernica* Williams, 1946 can be distinguished from *Leptidea sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758) by their genitalia (male or female), but *L. reali* and *L. juvernica* can only be reliably separated by barcoding.

The names assigned to these recently described species may still change, as they were previously confused with *L. sinapis*, a species to which numerous infraspecific taxa had been attributed.

2.2. What is the original status, authorship and date of *L. morsei*?

Two publications from 1882 compete for priority:

a) *Leucophasia morsei* Fenton, 1882. In: Ishikawa, *Papilio* 2(3): 35–36, fig 3-4. The publication date printed in the journal is March 1882.

b) *Leptosia morsei* Fenton, [1882]. In: Butler, *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 1881: 855. The publication date printed in the journal is 15 November 1881, but the actual distribution date was very likely in 1882.

There is therefore considerable uncertainty regarding the actual distribution dates of these works. The approach adopted here is to follow Bozano *et al.* (2016), the most recent monograph treating the Dismorphiinae of the Palearctic fauna.

2.3. Conclusion

In the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), *L. sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *L. reali* Reissinger, [1990], *L. juvernica* Williams, 1946, *L. duponcheli* (Staudinger, 1871) and *L. morsei* (Fenton, 1882) are adopted.

2.4. References

Bozano G., Coutsis J., Herman P., Allegrucci G., Cesaroni D. & Sbordoni V. 2016. *Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region*. Pieridae part 3, Subfamily Coliadinae (tribes Rhodocerini, Euremini and Catopsilia), Subfamily Dismorphiinae. — Milano: Omnes Artes (Ed.). 70 p.

Dincă V., Lukhtanov V., Talavera G. & Vila R. 2011. Unexpected layers of cryptic diversity in Wood White *Leptidea* butterflies. — *Nature Communications* 2(1): (324) 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1329>

Fenton M. [1882]. In: Butler A. G., On Butterflies from Japan; with which are incorporated Notes and Descriptions of new Species by Montague Fenton. — *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 1881: 846-856. ([url](#))

Fenton M. 1882. In: Ishikawa C., Notes on variations in some Japanese Lepidoptera. — *Papilio, Organ of the New York Entomological Club* 2(3): 35-37, fig. ([url](#))

Lorković Z. 1993. *Leptidea reali* Reissinger, 1989 (= *lorkovicii* Real 1988), a new European species (Lepid., Pieridae). — *Natura Croatica* 2(1): 1-26. ([url](#))

Mazel R. 2000. Le polymorphisme de deux « espèces-jumelles » *Leptidea sinapis* L. et *L. reali* Reissinger en France (Lepidoptera : Pieridae). — *Linneana Belgica* 17(7): 277-285. ([url](#))

Mazel R. 2001. Le polymorphisme de deux « espèces-jumelles » *Leptidea sinapis* L. et *L. reali* Reissinger en France (Lepidoptera : Pieridae), Deuxième partie. — *Linneana Belgica* 18(1): 37-43. ([url](#))

Mazel R. 2001. *Leptidea sinapis* L., 1758 – *L. reali* Reissinger, 1989, le point de la situation (Lepidoptera: Pieridae, Dismorphiinae). — *Linneana Belgica* 18(4): 199-202. ([url](#))

Mazel R. & Eitschberger U. 2002. Répartition géographique de *Leptidea sinapis* (L., 1758) et *L. reali* Reissinger, 1989 au nord de l'Europe, en Russie et dans quelques pays d'Asie (Lepidoptera: Pieridae, Dismorphiinae). — *Linneana Belgica* 18(8): 373-376. ([url](#))

Réal P. 1988. Lépidoptères nouveaux, principalement jurassiens. — *Mémoires du Comité de liaison pour les Recherches Ecofaunistiques dans le Jura* 4: 1-28. ([url](#))

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

3. Classification within the Genus *Gonepteryx* Leach, 1815

3.1. Introduction

The various species of this genus are relatively well known. Nevertheless, the specific status of the taxa from the Canary Islands remains uncertain, as the conclusions of several recent studies are somewhat divergent. The phylogenetic study of the genus by Brunton *et al.* (1998) concluded that three putative species occur in the Canary Islands: *Gonepteryx cleobule* (Hübner, [1824]), *G. eversi* Rehnelt, 1974 and *G. palmae* Stamm, 1963. Although Dapporto *et al.* (2022) recognise only a single species on these islands, *G. cleobule*, the figure depicting the haplotype network nonetheless reveals a significant separation among the three taxa proposed by Brunton *et al.* (1998). However, the barcoding data show a maximum p-distance of only 2.1% (corresponding to 11 mutations in the mitochondrial COI gene), based on a limited sample of 13 specimens from three islands. As no nuclear data are available, these results should be interpreted with caution.

In his monograph on the genus, Bozano *et al.* (2016) retain only two species for the Canary Islands, *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae*, and treat *G. eversi* as a subspecies of *G. cleobule*. Plates of male genitalia (by Coutsis J.) demonstrate that there is a significant difference in the structure of the male genitalia between *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae*. Are these differences sufficient to ensure reproductive isolation of these insular populations?

3.2. Conclusion

In the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae* are adopted for the *Gonepteryx* of the Canary Islands.

3.3. References

Bozano G., Coutsis J., Herman P., Allegrucci G., Cesaroni D. & Sbordoni V. 2016. *Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region*. Pieridae part 3, Subfamily Coliadinae (tribes Rhodocerini, Euremini and Catopsilia), Subfamily Dismorphiinae. — Milano: Omnes Artes (Ed.). 70 p.

Brunton C. & Hurst G. 1998. Mitochondrial DNA phylogeny of Brimstone butterflies (genus *Gonepteryx*) from the Canary Islands and Madeira. — *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 63(1): 69-79 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.1998.tb01639.x>

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 31: 2184-2190. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579>. Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

4. Classification within the Genus *Colias* Fabricius, 1807

4.1. Introduction

Colias represents a species-rich genus with a broad global distribution, but its internal classification has long been debated.

Early work by Berger (1986) examined the genus in detail and proposed a subdivision into several subgenera based primarily on the morphology of tergite 8.

Verhulst's extensive monograph (2000) took a complementary approach, relying predominantly on habitus and biological traits for species delimitation. While thorough in descriptive scope, this latter work did not incorporate a broader set of morphological or molecular characters, which may limit its ability to unravel evolutionary relationships and refine the systematics of the genus.

Significant nomenclatural efforts have since aimed to clarify the taxonomic foundation of the genus.

Grieshuber & Lamas (2007) compiled a synonymic list intended to provide a complete and authoritative account of all available names in *Colias*, acknowledging that many taxa remain provisionally interpreted in the absence of comprehensive evidence, and underscoring the difficulty of deciding whether phenotypically distinct populations represent full species or geographic races.

The annotated catalogue by Grieshuber, Worthy & Lamas (2012) further extended these efforts by examining type material from major museum collections and providing detailed taxonomic status for Old World taxa.

Prior to the advent of modern phylogenetic studies, few systematic treatments used criteria beyond morphology or ecology to differentiate species or subgenera.

Early phylogenetic work, often based on a restricted sampling of taxa and loci, produced results that were at times contradictory or unexpected with respect to subgroup delineation and evolutionary relationships.

This has highlighted the need for broader taxon sampling and multiple lines of evidence.

Only recently has a comprehensive phylogenetic study addressed this need: Mo *et al.* (2024) analysed a large dataset to assign confirmed species to well-supported clades and to investigate diversification across the genus.

The clades identified in this study correspond only partially to the subgenera proposed by Berger (1986), indicating that traditional morphological classifications, while informative, do not always fully reflect evolutionary relationships.

4.2. Conclusion

The subdivision of *Colias* into subgenera will require a full systematic revision of the genus. The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), will need to be updated regarding species arrangement on the basis of the results presented by Mo *et al.* (2024).

4.3. References

Berger L. 1986. Systématique du genre *Colias* F. Lepidoptera-Pieridae. — *Lambillionea* 86(7-8, suppl.): 1-68.

Grieshuber J. & Lamas G. 2007. A synonymic list of the genus *Colias* Fabricius, 1807 (Lepidoptera: Pieridae). — *Mitteilungen der münchener entomologischen Gesellschaft* 97:131-171. ([url](#))

Grieshuber J., Worthy B. & Lamas. 2012. *The genus Colias Fabricius, 1807. Jan Haugum's annotated catalogue of the Old World Colias*. — Tshikolovets Publications, Pardubice. 438 p.

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

Verhulst J. 2000. *Les Colias du Globe: Monograph of the Genus Colias*. — Keltern: Geock & Evers (ed.). 264 p.

Mo S., Braga M., Lohman D., Nylin S., Moumou A., Wheat C., Wahlberg N., Wang M., Ma F., Zhang P. & Wang H. 2024. Rapid Evolution of Host Repertoire and Geographic Range in a Young and Diverse Genus of Montane Butterflies. — *Systematic Biology* 74(1): 141-157. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sysbio/syae061>

5. Classification of the *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758) complex

5.1. Introduction

The *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758) complex comprises several taxa for which species status remains to be demonstrated. A comprehensive monograph covering all potential species (Eitschberger 1983) recognised the following species for the western Palaearctic region: *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pieris bryoniae* (Hübner, [1806]), *Pieris pseudorapae* Verity, 1908 which consists of three subspecies, *pseudorapae* Verity from Lebanon, *suffusa* Sheljuzhko, 1931 from southern Russia, and *balcana* Lorkovic, 1968 from the Balkans, and *Pieris segonzaci* Le Cerf, 1923. This study relied on a broad set of criteria, including ecology, habitus, the morphology of legs and androconia, male genitalia, eggs, and other characters, to establish the species listed above. Reissinger (1990), in his checklist, adopted Eitschberger's classification unchanged.

However, the results of hybridisation experiments (Lorkovic 1970; Hesselbarth *et al.* 1995) challenge this classification, as they showed that the Asia Minor and Caucasian taxa previously assigned to *P. pseudorapae* can freely hybridise with *P. napi*, whereas *balcana* cannot.

Dapporto *et al.* (2022), in *The Atlas of Mitochondrial Genetic Diversity for Western Palearctic Butterflies*, recognised the following species: *P. balcana*, *P. bryoniae*, *P. napi*, and *P. segonzaci*.

However, a recent genomic study posted as a bioRxiv preprint (Sala-Garcia *et al.* 2025) using broad phylogenomic and population genomic data across the *Pieris napi* group suggests patterns of phylogenetic relationships, population structure and ecological differentiation that may not fully align with purely mitochondrial or morphology-based taxonomies, and it highlights the need for further evaluation once the work has undergone formal peer review.

5.2. Conclusion

The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), is aligned with the taxonomic conclusions of the most recent peer-reviewed study.

5.3. References

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 31: 2184-2190. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579>. Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

- Eitschberger U. 1983. Systematische Untersuchungen am *Pieris napi-bryoniae*-Komplex (s.l.) (Lepidoptera, Pieridae). Band 1, Teil 1. — *Herbipoliana, Buchreihe zur Lepidopterologie* 1(1): 1-504. ([url](#))
- Eitschberger U. 1983. Systematische Untersuchungen am *Pieris napi-bryoniae*-Komplex (s.l.) (Lepidoptera, Pieridae). Band 1, Teil 2. — *Herbipoliana, Buchreihe zur Lepidopterologie* 1(2): 1-601. ([url](#))
- Hesselbarth G., van Oorschot H. & Wagener S. 1995. *Die Tagfalter der Türkei. Under Berücksichtigung der Angrenzende Länder*. 3 Vol. — Bocholt: Selbstverlag S. Wagener (Ed.). 2199 p.
- Lorković Z. 1968[1969]. Karyologischer Beitrag zur Frage der Fortpflanzungsverhältnisse südeuropäischer Taxone von *Pieris napi* (L.) (Lep., Pieridae). — *Bioloski Glasnik* 21(1-4): 95-136.
- Reissinger E. J. [1990]. Checkliste Pieridae Duponchel, 1835 (Lepidoptera) der Westpalaearktis (Europa, Nordwestafrika, Kaukasus, Kleinasien). — *Atalanta* 20: 149-185. ([url](#))
- Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>
- Sala-Garcia J., Vives-Inglá M., Tonzo V., Dincă V., Vila R. & Carnicer J. 2025. Phylogeography and diversification of the *Pieris napi* species group in the Western Palaeartic. — *bioRxiv* 2025.01.31.634921. ([url](#))

6. The position of the Genus *Belenois* Hübner, [1819] in the classification

6.1. Introduction

The study by Kawahara A. *et al.* (2023) provides evidence that the genus *Belenois* is a member of the subtribe Aporiina. As noted in point 1 above, the status of this subtribe has been revised, and it is now recognised as the tribe Aporiini.

6.2. Conclusion

The genus *Belenois* Hübner, [1819], together with its subgenus *Anaphaeis* Hübner, [1819], and its sole species recorded in the western Palaeartic, *Belenois aurota* (Fabricius, 1793), should consequently be positioned in the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), immediately after *Aporia crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758).

6.3. References

Kawahara A., Storer C., Carvalho A., Plotkin D., Condamine F., Braga M., Ellis E., St Laurent R., Li X., Barve V., Cai L., Earl C., Frandsen B., Owens H., Valencia-Montoya W., Aduse-Poku K., Toussaint E., Dexter K., Doleck T., Markee A., Messcher R., Nguyen Y., Badon J., Benítez H., Braby M., Buenavente P., Chan W., Collins S., Rabideau Childers R., Dankowicz E., Eastwood R., Fric Z., Gott R., Hall J., Hallwachs W., Hardy N., Hawkins Sipe R., Heath A., Hinolan J., Homziak N., Hsu Y., Inayoshi Y, Itliong M., Janzen D., Kitching I., Kunte K., Lamas G., Landis M., Larsen E., Larsen T., Leong J., Lukhtanov V., Maier C., Martinez J., Martins D., Maruyama K., Maunsell S., Mega N., Monastyrskii A., Morais A., Müller C., Naive M., Nielsen G., Padrón P., Peggie D., Romanowski H., Sáfián S., Saito M., Schröder S., Shirey V., Soltis D., Soltis P., Sourakov A., Talavera G., Vila R., Vlasanek P., Wang H., Warren A., Willmott K., Yago M., Jetz W., Jarzyna M., Breinholt J., Espeland M., Ries L., Guralnick R., Pierce N. & Lohman D. 2023. A global phylogeny of butterflies reveals their evolutionary history, ancestral hosts and biogeographic origins. — *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7: 903-913. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02041-9> . Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

7. Structure of the genera within the tribe Anthocharidini Scudder, 1889

7.1. Introduction

The tribe Anthocharodini constitutes a well-supported monophyletic clade, clearly distinct from the Pierini (Kawahara A.Y. *et al.* 2023). Nonetheless, the internal generic structure of this tribe has been the focus of several competing and markedly divergent hypotheses. Tracing back to Higgins (1975), the classification of genera, based primarily on male genitalia morphology, was as follows: *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819] (including *tagis* (Hübner, [1804])), *Elphinstonia* Klots, 1930, *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslín, [1833], and *Zegrís* Boisduval, 1836. Between 1979 and 2013, Back conducted extensive studies on the biology of numerous species within this group and published multiple papers reporting his findings, without revising the generic framework.

The studies by Back, Knebelberger and Miller (2006, 2008), however, fundamentally reshaped the overall framework of this group. First, the genus *Iberochloe* Back, Knebelberger and Miller, 2008, was established to accommodate two species, *tagis* Hübner, [1804], and *pechi* Staudinger, 1885. For clarity, a concise summary of the various proposed generic arrangements within the tribe is presented below:

Back, Knebelberger & Miller (2008): *Euchloe* + ((*Iberochloe* + *Anthocharis*) + *Elphinstonia*)

Back, Miller & Opler (2011): *Euchloe* + ((*Iberochloe* + *Elphinstonia*) + *Anthocharis*)

Back (2020: 10): (*Euchloe* + (*Zegris* + *Elphinstonia*)) + (*Anthocharis* + *Iberochloe*)

Kawahara A. *et al.* (2023): (*Anthocharis* + *Euchloe*) + *Zegris*

In view of these alternative hypotheses, Marabuto *et al.* (2020) recommended, as a taxonomic outcome of their study, retaining *Euchloe*, *Elphinstonia* and *Iberochloe* as subgenera of *Euchloe*. Dapporto *et al.* (2022) recognise only three genera, listed alphabetically as *Anthocharis*, *Euchloe* and *Zegris*, and treat the species assigned by Back (2020) and Marabuto *et al.* (2020), both at subgeneric level, to *Iberochloe* and *Elphinstonia* as members of *Euchloe*.

7.2. Conclusion

Views on the delimitation and hierarchical rank of genera within the tribe remain diverse and, in several cases, mutually contradictory. In the face of this ongoing instability, the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), follows the generic and specific framework adopted by Dapporto *et al.* (2022), with two exceptions. The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), includes *Euchloe pechi* (Staudinger, 1885), as the genetic divergence reported in that study is relatively substantial and its habitus is highly distinctive. However, this placement remains provisional, as Back (1984) demonstrated that Algerian and European populations exhibit an exceptionally high degree of reproductive compatibility, with natural copulation occurring readily and no developmental anomalies or particular susceptibilities observed in the offspring.

Back (2020) treated *Zegris meridionalis* (Lederer, 1853) as a valid species. In line with Dapporto *et al.* (2022), the present checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), considers *meridionalis* to be a subspecies of *Zegris eupheme* (Esper, [1804]).

7.3. References

Back W. 1979. Zur Biologie der europäischen und nordwestafrikanischen Populationen von *Euchloe ausonia* Hübner 1804 (Lep. Pieridae). — *Atalanta* 10(3): 225-243. ([url](#))

Back W. 1984. Beschreibung der Präimaginalstadien von *Euchloe tagis pechi* Staudinger, 1885* (Lep. Pieridae). — *Atalanta* 15(1-2): 152-164. ([url](#))

Back W. 1991. Taxonomische Untersuchungen innerhalb der Artengruppe um *Euchloe ausonia* (Hübner, 1804) (Lepidoptera, Pieridae). — *Atalanta* 21(3/4): 187-206. ([url](#))

Back W. 2013. Verbreitung von *Euchloe ausonia* (Hübner, 1804), *Euchloe daphalis* (Moore, 1865) und *Euchloe persica* Verity, 1908 stat. nov. im Iran. — *Atalanta* 44: 109-117.

Back W. 2020. In: Bozano G. *Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region*. Pieridae part 4, Subfamily Pierinae (partim), Tribe Anthocharidini. — Milano: Omnes Artes (Ed.). 102 p.

Back W., Knebelberger T. & Miller M.A. 2006. The phylogenetic relationships of the species and subspecies of the subgenus *Elphinstonia* Klots, 1930 (Lepidoptera, Pieridae). — *Atalanta* 37(3/4): 469-482. ([url](#))

Back W., Knebelberger T. & Miller M.A. 2008. Molekularbiologische Untersuchungen und Systematik der paläarktischen Arten von *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819] (Lepidoptera: Pieridae). — *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 118(4): 147-169.

Back W., Miller M. A. & Opler P. A. 2011. Genetic, Phenetic, and Distributional Relationships of Nearctic *Euchloe* (Pieridae, Pierinae, Anthocharidini). — *The Journal of the Lepidopterists' Society* 65(1): 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.18473/lepi.v65i1.a1>

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 31: 2184-2190. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579>. Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

Higgins L. 1975. *The Classification of European Butterflies*. — London: Collins (Ed.). 320 p.

Kawahara A., Storer C., Carvalho A., Plotkin D., Condamine F., Braga M., Ellis E., St Laurent R., Li X., Barve V., Cai L., Earl C., Frandsen B., Owens H., Valencia-Montoya W., Aduse-Poku K., Toussaint E., Dexter K., Doleck T., Markee A., Messcher R., Nguyen Y., Badon J., Benítez H., Braby M., Buenavente P., Chan W., Collins S., Rabideau Childers R., Dankowicz E., Eastwood R., Fric Z., Gott R., Hall J., Hallwachs W., Hardy N., Hawkins Sipe R., Heath A., Hinolan J., Homziak N., Hsu Y., Inayoshi Y., Itliong M., Janzen D., Kitching I., Kunte K., Lamas G., Landis M., Larsen E., Larsen T., Leong J., Lukhtanov V., Maier C., Martinez J., Martins D., Maruyama K., Maunsell S., Mega N., Monastyrskii A., Morais A., Müller C., Naive M., Nielsen G., Padrón P., Peggie D., Romanowski H., Sáfián S., Saito M., Schröder S., Shirey V., Soltis D., Soltis P., Sourakov A., Talavera G., Vila R., Vlasanek P., Wang H., Warren A., Willmott K., Yago M., Jetz W., Jarzyna M., Breinholt J., Espeland M., Ries L., Guralnick R., Pierce N. & Lohman D. 2023. A global phylogeny of butterflies reveals their evolutionary history, ancestral hosts and biogeographic origins. — *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7: 903-913. Article: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02041-9> . Supplementary Materials: [url](#).

Marabuto E., Pina-Martins F., Rebelo M. & Paulo O. 2020. Ancient divergence, a crisis of salt and another of ice shaped the evolution of the west Mediterranean butterfly *Euchloe tagis*. — *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 131(3): 487–504. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnean/blaa129>

Taymans M. & Cuvelier S. A dynamic checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea). — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* 2025(1): 1-70. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14733224>

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Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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